

Report ethical, social, theological, technical review of 1st generation PES algorithms and data use

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to support the development of a disruptive technology, by examining incumbent technologies used in some Public Employment Services (PES), what we term first generation algorithmic profiling tools. So, here we report on an ethical, social, theological, technical review of thirteen state of the art deployments, unpicking their general approach to offer a detailed understanding of incumbent approaches.

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1.0 Introduction

Contemporary Public Employment Services (PES) are rapidly transforming to exploit IT and deploy new software tools for data-collection, mining, exchange, communication and collaboration. Driving this is the policy objectives of reducing long term unemployment and increasing labour market participation.

While almost all PES policy operates as an algorithmic rule-based system, the past twenty years has seen the renewal of profiling techniques using the big datasets captured in PES interrogated using algorithmic techniques. Prior to algorithmic profiling, some PES engaged in casework-led profiling or rule-based profiling and so the transformation is to black-box these visible processes, sometimes removing the casework/human right to override the algorithm's decision. In many other cases, the international trend for algorithmic profiling has led to the introduction of profiling into more universalistic systems. With some variations, algorithmic profiling has renewed and greatly increased the use of profiling in PES, in general bluntly identifying recipients of a passive PES or an active PES, based on the algorithm identifying those with a statistically having a high probability of becoming long-term unemployed.

Long-term unemployment (LTU) has been identified as having a significant scarring effect (Arulampalam, 2001). Depending on the particular PES, LTU is defined as being unemployed for either six or twelve months. Unemployment is tightly defined concept that is operationalised statistically and administratively – it stems from the 1954 ILO definition- individuals not working, available for work and seeking work; and accepted by over 165 Governments. Scarring elides a workable definition (Bivens, 2014) as it is a vulgate metaphorical term to capture the badness of LTU that macroeconomists associate with loss of output and rising non-accelerating inflation rate of unemployment (NAIRU), sociologists consider a threat to social cohesion as LTU is associated with exclusion from society. Most other uses of scarring capture the impact on unemployed individuals rather than broad damage to society and economy. So public health researchers associate LTU with lower life expectancy and worse morbidity outcomes (Virtanen et al., 2013; Strandh et al, 2014), microeconomists associate it with lower lifetime income (Ruhm, 1991, Gangl, 2006), and psychologists associate it with a rise in mental illness (indeed some have recommended its inclusion in Diagnostic and Statistical Manual 6 DSM as a psychosocial disorder (DSM-IV-TR, 2000)) Notwithstanding the definitional imprecision of scarring, it captures the view that LTU is bad for the economy, for society and for the individuals stuck in that situation.

The perpetual concern for those lost from the world of work has also been identified as more a theological imperative, than a practical or necessarily efficient concern. In this sense identifying those at risk of LTU is not simply a matter of fine-tuning rules, processes and institutions within the state, but follows cultural models. While political discussions often focus on the costs of welfare payments and their impact on the economy, compartmentalising the problem in sociology, psychology, economics or social policy and care; these all reflect a deeper concern; the lives, the behaviour, the very being of those who claim welfare payments. Ideas like 'incentives', 'culture of dependency' or 'human capital' may initially seem like academic abstractions, but they reflect long-standing historical models. Policies which are abstractly described as 'labour market reforms' or 'activation' are attempts to transform individuals: whether through sticks and carrots of incentives or education and training, the aim is to reshape the attitudes, behaviour and decisions of individuals; it is an attempt at 'reform' – to purify and save the individual. The map rather than the lived terrain of the unemployed person is held in focus whilst these reforms are addressed. Policy makers are increasingly carefully avoid moralising and religious language, but they are explicit about their aim of transforming the unemployed into active job-seekers. Obviously, there are differences of emphasis, for instance, between those who focus on incentives – which implies the unemployed are lazy, feckless and greedy, or have too much pride to take humble work and therefore need reformation – and those who focus on so-called 'culture of poverty' or 'welfare dependency' arguments which also imply the unemployed need to be transformed by re-education in the 'work-ethic'. Recognising that the ideas that animate

the algorithm are shaped at least partially by religious ideas or 'economic theology' (Agamben, 2011; Dean; 2019; Schwarzkopf, 2020, Boland and Griffin, 2021) may help us to understand them better.

For all of these reasons, PES tries to separate the treatment of frictional unemployment from structural unemployment so that they can direct expensive interventions to where they perceive that they are needed most. PES are attracted to using *public service judgement algorithms* as they presents as an objective method of segmenting the population of unemployed, appearing to take the human element out of judging people and they are cheap to administer to large populations quickly. There are multiple other information technology systems within PES that support file management, decision supports systems, auditing and reporting, and job matching- these are beyond the scope of this review. Rather, this paper is focused on learning from specific PES deployments of computer modelling of the labour market used in decision support systems, using various statistical profiling approaches; and aspires to offer some foundational tenets for designing ethical PES algorithms based an ethical, social, theological, technical review of first generation algorithms and data use.

The developments of these PES algorithms are being driven by advances in computing and technology, which have enabled systems to handle complex processing in support of decision-making. At the same time, emerging developments in machine learning hold out the possibility of algorithms learning from data and reacting to new scenarios never explicitly encountered or considered by their authors. As the pervasiveness of computer based decision-making capabilities in PES continues to increase, there is an ever greater potential for ethical failures with significant impacts. The development of PES algorithms requires careful consideration of the ethical context of the system, and how best to address these new forms of risk. If ethics are not properly addressed during design, implementation, and use, they can accelerate unwanted biases and erode human trust in the systems, PES, government and polity that deploy them, and alter the social compact within society. Practitioners designing PES algorithms that will become a key part of social protection infrastructure must take these risks into account.

In our review we draw extensively on work by the OECD and PESnetwork on individual countries experience of developing and deploying profiling algorithms (Desiere et al., 2019). In particular we rely on two Technical Assistance and Information Exchange instrument (TAIEX) workshops kindly organised by the European Commission- on "statistical profiling tools for effective targeting and tailoring of services to jobseekers" (SRSP 68969 on 1.8.20 and 8.10.20). These provided in-depth briefings with Q&A sessions on various country implementations and were complimented by similar interactive presentations from the Slovenian PES experts. The report was prepared against the backdrop of a significant rise in unemployment resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, which both impacted our programme of work and the context in which all briefings and research was undertaken. Presently a sharp structural rise in unemployment is predicted in the enduring and hoped for aftermath of the pandemic, and this will renew pressure on PES to support individuals back into work- this focuses our efforts on developing a useful, impactful disruptive tool for PES and unemployed people to use.

Specifically we reviewed the following longlist of learning cases:

Country	Ambition	Method	Self-reported efficacy	Source
Ireland- PEX	Identifying those at risk of LTU (6 mths)	Probit regression	50-69%	O'Connell, McGuinness, Kelly, & Walsh (2009) Griffin, Boland, Tuite & Hennessy (2020)
Austria- AMAS	Identifying those at risk of S/M/L TU (3/7/24 mths)	Logistic regression	80-85%	Desiere, Langenbucher, Struyven (2019)
Denmark- Job Barometer	Identifying those at risk of LTU (6 mths)	Logistic regression	66%	Roshol, Svarer & Hammer (2004); Madsen (2014); Larsen, Brigitte &Jonsson (2011)
France- Intelligence	Identifying those at risk of LTU (6 months)	Neural network	70-80%	OWALGROUP (2019)

Emploi				
Australia- JSCI	Identifying those at risk of LTU (12 mths)	Logistic regression	Not reported	Ponomareva & Sheen (2013); Lipp, (2005)
Croatia- StAP	Identifying those at risk of LTU (12 mths)	Logistic regression	69%	Botrić (2017) Flesicher (2016)
Finland- Risk Profiling Tool	Identifying those at risk of LTU (12 mths)	Logistic regression	89%	Riipinen (2011); Behncke et al., (2007)
Belgium- VDAB	Identifying those at risk of LTU (6 mths)	Random forest	67%	Desiere, Langenbucher, Struyven (2019)
Estonia- Soft Profiling	ALMP effect	Statistical model	Not reported	Van Ours (2007) Brixiova & Egert (2012)
Italy	Identifying those at risk of LTU (12 mths)	Logistic regression	70-90%	OECD (2019a)
Latvia	Identifying those at risk of LTU (12 mths)	Factor analysis	60-70%	Desiere, Langenbucher, Struyven (2019) OECD (2019b)
Netherlands- WorkProfiler	Identifying those at risk of LTU (12 mths)	Logistic regression	70%	Wijnhoven and Havinga (2014); Hasluck (2008)
New Zealand- SEM	Identifying those at risk of LTU (6 mths)	Random Forrest and Gradient boosting	63-83%	Ministry for Social Development (2018)
Sweden-AST	Identifying those at risk of LTU (6 mths)	Logistic regression	85-90%	Loxha & Morgandi (2014)

Adapted from Desiere, Langenbucher, Struyven (2019) and Georges (2008)

We then focus our review on five 'state of the art' of PES algorithms (Ireland, Austria, Croatia, France, and Australia), selected on their relevance and our ability to access in-depth information. A prior Irish Research Council study of Ireland's PEX algorithm inspired the HECAT project, the other countries all presented at the TAIEX event. From all this work, we consider the generic structure of these tools and problematising their ethical, social, theological, technical review of such 1st generation PES algorithms and data use.

Generic structure LTU sorting/profiling algorithms

Our baseline study reviews five 'state of the art' of PES algorithms. As these systems become ever more pervasive, it is vital that they be devised thoughtfully and ethically. This requires a deep understanding of the history, ambitions, and context of PES and the experience of unemployment, exploring the social, theological and technical aspects of societies efforts rendered practically in PES. In the absence of this work it is left to chance as to whether this technical transformation is an

improvement or an impoverishment, and whether these algorithm represents social progress and do not risk harm to individuals.

Naturally, this report is infused with the privileges, limitations and biases that arise from where it was produced, and who did the producing. The work was conducted in Ireland, entirely by Irish people and is steeped in the peculiarly Judaeo-Christian, post-colonial, halfway between Berlin and Boston heritage. Until recently, the Irish labour market was substantially a liberal, male breadwinner model, with significant emphasis on charity, moral pressure and emigration to resolve the considerable labour market failures that antagonised the country. From this maelstrom emerged a highly liberal model based on competing for global capital, high productivity and social progress through labour market inclusivity. Foolish to think that despite efforts to engage internationally, extensively over many years that we can transcend that deep cultural coding. Rather we acknowledge it here, at the outset, and aspire to check ourselves and opinions in this process, recognising that much of our cultural inheritance has marginalised other voices; and so we pay particular attention to listening and being open.

1.1 Introduction to terms

Many of terms in this report are slippery fish (O'Carroll, 1987), terms that have precise technical meanings in various disciplines, sometimes conflicting definitions, and when used in public scholarship often are used unreflectively and ambiguously that antithetical to the precise definition. Here we introduce some the more significant terms in this report.

Active labour market policies (ALMPs)

ALMPs is the term for a family government measures that intervene in the labour market to assist unemployed people find work. ALMPs are work-first policy actions to increase 'labour market participation' – either by providing jobseekers with employability orientated training or education – 'human capital building', or by putting pressure on them to find and accept work, measures referred to as 'welfare conditionality'. ALMPs reform in two ways, intervening in individual lives to reform conduct, but equally intervening in existing, 'passive' welfare institutions that rendered the unemployed 'welfare dependent'. There is no standard mix of ALMP measures, but they tend to include regular case-officer meetings, group engagement, psychological and algorithmic profiling, motivational or CV workshops, extensive monitored job-searches, and organised recruitment. Standard histories trace ALMPs to the post-war Swedish Rehn-Meidner policies, where activation policies were seen as important approach to achieve 'social inclusion'. Such policies advanced to standard PES practice from their early adoption in the USA, with a considerably tougher approach to conditionality, then spread to Australia, the UK and became broadly encouraged by the OECD from the 1990s, becoming EU-wide policy by the end of the century. Notable examples include welfare reforms under Tony Blair's New Labour-third way policies, the Hartz reforms in Germany and Sarkozy's attempts at sweeping reforms of the French welfare system (Hansen, 2019).

Algorithms

In mathematics and computer science, the term 'algorithm' means an unambiguous procedure for solving a problem — 'a finite, abstract, effective, compound control structure, imperatively given, accomplishing a given purpose under given provisions' (Hill 2016: 47). As Seaver (2013) points out, this technical understanding leads computer scientists and indeed many commercial and statutory bodies to view algorithms 'to be strictly rational concerns, marrying the certainties of mathematics with the objectivity of technology' (Seaver, 2013, p. 2). However increasingly a group of 'outsiders' driven by concerns about how algorithms work in the 'real world' have pushed the boundaries of how we understand algorithms pointing to the contingent, contextual nature of their design and implementation. Furthermore, algorithms are designed for specific purposes which by their nature are

not politically, socially, or economically neutral. Structuring preferences, dictating behaviour, identifying, sorting and classifying individuals are all profoundly political, social and economic activities with correspondingly profound ethical implications. Therefore to understand what algorithms are, we need to look far beyond the technical descriptions and consider the socio-technical nature of these mathematical formulae. In this report, we primarily use 'algorithm' to mean an automatic classification tool. Automated suggests once designed, the system of classification is run with little or no human involvement in classification, and often, the implication of that classification is to trigger a set of further procedures.

Data

For simplicity, in this report we use the contemporary empirical science definition of data as encoded information about one or more target phenomena. Data has however an archaic meaning, datum, from the Latin, dare, to give, means a thing given- literally a gift, a thing given from the natural world. Such a gift entangles us in cycles of generosity, exchange and reciprocity (Ingold, 2018). In contemporary empirical science, produced from the enlightenment mode of objective, rational knowledge production nested in British empiricism of Bacon, Loake, Berkley and Hume data is extracted, rather than received. It is extracted clinically so as to avoid contaminating the field. This generally means numerical data that becomes separated from context, meaning and the network of social relations; this data is extracted rather than given. For scientists even to admit to a relationship of give and take between themselves and their with the things in the world with which he deals would be enough to disqualify the inquiry and any insights arising from it.

Disruptive technology

This is a term that cascades towards us from the Harvard Business School Professor Clayton Christensen's book 'the innovators dilemma (1997), renewing interest in Schumpeterian concept of creative destruction (1942) and Kuhnian paradigm shifts (1962). Christensen's concept of disruptive technology explains a specific type of technological change, with a specific mechanism and consequences, and is now the mainstream thesis on the process by which new technologies eventually displace established technologies. The value of this process view (Whitehead, 1919) is that it explains the institutional and contextual support for prior technology, the cycle by which emerging technology initially underperforms market expectations and how the trajectory of rising performance of alternative technologies can reconstitute a market, product or service. In particular the concept of disruptive technology leads to exploring how new technologies tend to gain traction by exploiting singular weaknesses of incumbent solutions and then develop and mature to meet the needs of the broad market. Those reliant on incumbent technology tend to work incrementally to sustain their technology investments and infrastructure, and are thus poorly positioned to catch up with lead disruptors (Chesbrough, 2001; Christensen and Raynor, 2003).

Ethical, social, theological, technical

We adopt a broad definition of 'ethical, social, theological, technical' for our review, to explore the ways that algorithms and various forms of data can impact society, and how these impacts can advance or undermine widely shared values. We consciously use the term 'review' to reflect on our holistic concerns for positive as well as negative impacts of these technologies,. This is crucial, as in our conclusion we emphasise the importance of considering the tensions that arise between the potential opportunities and hazards of using technologies based on algorithms and data.

Ethics

We use the term ethics in this report to capture values and commitments that are deeply-held and reasonably widely-shared. This project is funded by the European Union, and so the project is in furtherance of the ethics and values of that institution. Europe does not have a written constitution, and so the values, goals and ideals are not assembled into an uncontested and legitimate statement. Indeed, a defining feature of the European ethics is the inability to complete a constitutional process, and yet to stay in endless peaceful political dialogue. The course of Europe, hewn from Greek thought, Roman law, religions of books, empires, devastating territorial, colonial and world wars, now follows a

political adventure of joined destinies, diverse and common (Latour, 2005). Two passages of the Bruno Latour's draft constitution are worth quoting for their resonance (Rosa, 2019) with a coherent European ethic.

Redistribution of the attributes of sovereignty:

We, as old European nations, have extracted all the advantages of the national State, but paid by centuries of fratricidal war the full cost of those advantages. We are conscious of how deeply the peoples of Europe are attached - and rightly so - to the slow formation of their sovereignty. But we are still more conscious of the plasticity of these forms of common life. It is in the certainty of remaining faithful to our particular histories that we have pledged ourselves to a unique undertaking. That undertaking will call back into question and redistribute one by one all the attributes and symbols of sovereignty. We are certain that, despite the change of scale, the sense of security and of belonging, which is so indispensable to civic life, can be regained.

The role of economy:

We, as old European nations, invented political economy and then, by means of market organisations, set in motion a previously unknown prosperity. Having suffered, and caused the entire planet to suffer, from the still more dreadful ravages caused by the forms of totalitarianism which they claimed to overcome, we solemnly swear to set up institutions that will re-establish economic organisations solely in democratic forms capable of defining the common good. The time has come for economic science - that secular religion - to be at last separated from the demands of State.

Labour Market

In precise economic terms, the labour market, or job market, refers to the supply of and demand for labour, in which employees provide the supply and employers provide the demand. The very idea of the 'labour market' is problematic, the notion of a rational economic model that neutrally represents the buying and selling of labour power; trading in people's time, bodies, effort and toil, thoughts and creativity, sometimes even their hearts and souls. Work is a lived experience, full of banter, rosters, hidden hierarchies, from swinging the lead, to the deep and profound moments of care across the work-scape of the various petty incivilities, hurts, joys and victories; and so is not a simple matter of economic exchange. It is a market in which market failure, and the impacts of market failure on individuals, employers and economies cannot be left to the brutality of the clearing function; and so the regulation and orchestration of the labour market is matter for Government. The labour market is also a deeply troubled, contested political space that addresses inequality, the working poor, precarious work, dirty work, unemployment, redundancy/scrapheapism, migrant labour, illegal labour, immaterial labour, alienation and anomie, breaking out across the world. The very concept of the 'labour market' artificially yokes disparate things together, particularly unemployment, jobseeking and work, and the space where flows between these things occur. The concept of labour market therefore is only ever glimpsed as the places and spaces where these flows happen are diffused and opaque.

2.0 Reviewing the archetypical profiling algorithms

This section reviews the archetypical first generation PES profiling algorithms, which are further contextualised in the following section, section 3 which explores five key exemplar cases of how algorithms have been designed and used in the context of particular countries. When taken together, despite their differences, each algorithm is connected to a profiling tool used by the leviathan state to ration care. We offer a summary of their essential similarities below.

- Animating each implementation is a concern for the scarring effect of LTU.
- They reflected the tension that PES' experience when their fixed capacity is confronted with a spike in unemployment and LTU and their desire to keep casework ratio to a manageable 1:150.
- These models reflect the inclination by PES organisations to use the normal registry data in their possession to systematically provide two levels of support based on perceived need - typically gender, age, health, marital status, spousal earnings, education, numeracy and literacy, employment and unemployment history and duration, urban/rural and county location of residence, willingness to move, access to transport (private and public).
- They less commonly include soft skills, such as critical thinking, time management, and / or communications skills as these are harder to measure and metricise.
- The data upon which many models are based is a cause of considerable frustration, with several countries identifying restrictions in the sample sizes and demography of their data.
- Statistical profiling is based on the econometric analysis of survey or PES registry demographic and socioeconomic data on job seekers to predict their probability of long-term unemployment, mostly using regression (logit and probit models) analysis which measure probabilities in relation to the jobseeker.
- The algorithm usually has a low to middling reported accuracy and a human override, meaning that case workers can change which category people are placed into.
- Profiling is based on thinly extracted data from unemployed people, often without reference to why it is taken, and with limited scope for unemployed people to shape the data they present and how it is used.
- Profiling rarely includes unemployed people's needs or aspirations, job quality metrics or information about labour demand.

So unlike prominent commercial algorithms (such as those used by Google, Netflix, Spotify, Amazon and Facebook), as a clear 'public relevance algorithm' (Gillespie, 2014) it cannot elide discussions of public good, ethics, procedural justice and fairness. With such tremendous agency in vulnerable people's lives, these algorithms demonstrate how "authority is being increasingly expressed algorithmically" (Pasquale, 2015:8), how agency is delegated by individuals and organisations to algorithms.

2.1 Archetypical profiling

The origin of these algorithms lies in the nexus of relations between PES, economists, data scientists and international benchmarking agencies. The attraction to these instruments is that they dehumanise the discrimination, throwing the unpleasant business of sorting citizens into a black box. In the next section, we pry open the black box to explore each of the elements of being processed through the algorithm. Before considering the overall social life of the algorithms.

archetypal LTU sorting/profiling algorithms whereby unemployed people's attributes are fed into a model, which then defines them as at risk of LTU or not, which determines if they receive additional supports

2.2.1 Unemployed person and jobseeking

Unemployment is a twentieth century invention, which, since its formulation has gently transformed over time as politics, policy, and social philosophies change. This section offers a brief history of this invention, and how the legacy of its creation continues to affect policy and decision-making today.

Since 1954 the International Labour Organization (ILO) has defined unemployed people as not working, available for work and seeking work. It went without saying at the time, unemployment was almost entirely conceived around a vision of ablest-male-breadwinner worklessness; and has gradually and not convincingly changed to include others. This ILO narrow definition of unemployment is apophatic, in the way that unemployment is a linguistic sense defined by what it is not – the unemployed are the residuum of the labour market. Given the institutional pressures around the production of that definition, it eschews a broader, more qualitative definition of the experience of unemployment. More colloquial definitions of unemployed tend to incorporate the experience of being unemployed, so for example unemployment has been called idleness (Russell, 1958), laziness (Lafargue, 1883), non-market activity (Brown et al., 1998), anti-work (Gorz, 1999) and more distantly feckless skiving and scrounging (Howe, 1998); but the ILO definition navigates around the more judgemental concept of unemployment as a *failure of a person rather than the labour market*.

To offer a detailed genealogy of the term unemployment would be a bold endeavour beyond the scope of this report, but in broad brush strokes the term came into common use in the context of a crisis, in the aftermath of the First World War. Earlier terms such as jobless, surplus labour and reserve army of labour captured variations of the term, but precision arose in parallel with the formation of the ILO. The ILO, now an agency of the UN, was founded in 1919 through the negotiations for the Versailles Treaty as a tripartite organisation of workers, employers, and governments to shape labour standards. In the preamble to its 1919 constitution, the ILO set out to prevent unemployment and improve working conditions. Soon after its foundation it set about developing rubrics for the production and communication of statistical information around unemployment, the setting up of public employment agencies in member states and the establishment of social insurance schemes to provide for the unemployed. Since then it has broadly interpreted its mission to 'combat unemployment' (ILO, 2014) working to promote administration and legislation that protects and improves working conditions and standards of living amongst its 175 member states. The new definition had a symbolic as well as a practical impact, with unemployed people now framed as unfortunate individuals in the labour market, rather than morally corrupt; and thus, unemployment was now a social problem demanding political action. Today, the ILO definition of unemployment continues to have tremendous currency and legitimacy as the definitive definition.

Despite constituting a settled definition, the ILO definition is problematic on a number of grounds. It is a 'thin description', meaning that the facts that it presents are decontextualised (Geertz, 1973). The definition of unemployment, rather than an eternal category, has an origin and history, like other research problems. Dewey (1938) saw research endeavours as emerging through moments of confusion and conflict, with these being proposed solutions for resolving them, indeed this is a *verba concepta* for the European Union. Simply put, the value of the ILO definition of unemployment is that it ignores the complexity and indeterminacy of social life as it shoehorns people into a simple category that is artificial, reductive, and globalised. More specifically, the ILO definition rests on a shifting understanding of what is and is not work. The concepts of work and non-work are presented as ahistorical facts, yet there have been radical changes to what we understand as work. Far removed from the industrial toil of agricultural work and industrial work at the time of the Industrial Revolution, work no longer resembles the historical rhetoric on employment. New forms of post-Fordist, post-industrial and post-modern work have emerged. Similar but ideologically distinct approaches to describe analogous phenomenon have emerged also (Bell, 1973 ; Castells, 1996 ; Drucker, 1959; Kalleberg, 2003 ; Machlup, 1962). For example some forms of work have become 'immaterial labour' (Hardt and Negri, 2000 ; Lazzarato, 1996), which is an attempt to designate contemporary activities of the emotional, affective and linguistic efforts with information technologies as new work. All of this serves to render the distinction between work and non-work as politically contested, particularly around contemporary discourses on precarious work, domestic work, and caring work. In this line of thinking, work is a cultural category of significance (Sharrock and Anderson, 1986 ; Woolgar, 1988) and recognition (Honneth, 2004) rather than a concrete objective fact, and unemployment is a broader, more qualitative experience than the fixed ILO definition allows for, evident in how colloquial definitions of unemployment such as 'on the dole' or 'laid off' tend to incorporate the experience of being unemployed. Central to the conceptualisation of unemployment is that 'work' is defined by monetary exchange, which is a crude indicator of economic activity. The ILO defines 'in employment' as 'persons who worked for an hour or more for payment or profit in the week preceding the survey, including those working on family farms or in family businesses'. In this line of thinking, the only work of value is that which produces monetary exchange and thus is amenable to statistical recording. Such a reductionist definition de-values non-monetary exchange – the informal reciprocity that underpins much of economic and social life (Mauss, 2002). Whilst it is clear that the ILO must strive towards something with a chance of statistical precision, such a definition, when institutionalised into a social welfare system, encourages individuals to disengage from forms of reciprocity and labour that are socially valuable.

The 1970s experience of stagflation associated with structurally higher levels of unemployment and a rising concern for welfare dependency (Demazière & Delpierre, 2020), shifted the balance of the definition with greater focus and PES effort on monitoring, enforcing and encouraging the actively seeking work element of the definition. These transformations reorientated the label unemployed into jobseekers and renewed the ambivalences and tensions of the apparatus of the welfare state at the point at which it provides care and a safety net.

Central to this transformation was the introduction of Active Labour Market Policies (ALMPs) by which the state operationalises the 'active' element of seeking (see section 1.1). Since their emergence in the anglophone countries of Australia, the USA and the UK, and the broadening to most OECD countries, ALMPs have spread and diversified, through increasingly conditional elements of cash transfers, particularly in Mexico and Brazil, whereby benefit rights depend on individuals conforming with norms around education and health (Peck and Theodore, 2016). The social policy process of ALMPs involves designing measures to reform individuals (Boland & Griffin, 2021), assessing whether this has been effective, and then refining and fine-tuning policy measures through cycles of policy evaluation and further reform. ALMPs call on reform of both individuals and the state through continuous optimisation by whatever means, and today algorithmic profiling and 'nudge' methods from behavioural economics are increasingly used to refine the mix of interventions (Friedli & Stearn, 2016; Struyven, 2019).

Unemployment assume the provision of welfare entitlements as automatic stabilisers in society and for individuals to passively hold them outside the labour market; the logic of ALMPs assumes that the problem of unemployment is the passivity of the unemployed and thus these people need to be

'activated'. Such policies arise in response to the provision of universal state-funded welfare benefits to the unemployed, entitlements that sit outside of the systems of contributory 'social insurance'. The persuasiveness of ALMPs, particularly in America is connected to the critique of the welfare state articulated by Von Hayek (1935; 1944) which emerged as the welfare state was being developed; a critique popularised by Milton Friedman (2002). Amid these various 'neoliberal' critics attempting to 'dismantle the welfare state' – as the standard left-wing assessment goes, there are very few who advocating the elimination of welfare payments. Primarily, ALMPs accept that welfare payments are a necessary support to a volatile economy and labour market. Thus, there is a tension inherent within ALMPs, between supplying economic support to individuals and encouraging job-seeking behaviour to support 'labour market participation'. Paradoxically, it is only through the provision of support, but making it conditional on behaviour – attendance at meetings, developing a resume, raising applications for jobs, engaging in retraining – that welfare offices can wield authority over the unemployed. While Hayek and Friedman critique of the welfare state drew on classical liberalism – the critique also aspired to suspend unemployed individuals right to choose; liberal choice in their radical schema was an entitlement preserved for those financially independent of the state. From their political economy orientated assault on the basic premise of the welfare state, other academic discourses have been instrumental in steering ALMPs, most obviously behavioural economics, social policy and sociology.

Demands to reform the welfare state have been most prominent in the USA, where the fear that it generates a perverse incentive to refuse work, deprives people of their American dream through generating a welfare trap animates policy. In this critique, welfare recipients are seen as strategic actors who loaf on the Government, and simultaneously victims of having their agency to shape their own lives stolen from them by the state. For instance, Charles Murray (2006) suggests that some young men 'prefer' doles to work, or that some women use pregnancy as a strategy to assure welfare support- 'welfare queens' is the popular parlance. In a similar vein, Andrew Dunn (2014) described the 'choosiness' of UK welfare recipients who refused any and all work, a view echoed in the political marketing of the UK Conservative party (Watts and Fitzpatrick, 2018, Dwyer, 2019).

The key figure in the practical development of ALMPs is Lawrence Mead (1986, 1997, 1993), a prominent political-activist-to-researcher. His series of polemical policy books and policy experiments in Wisconsin and New York have shaped welfare policy in the United States and beyond. A speechwriter for American President Richard Nixon, Mead was a policy advisor to Republican Party on welfare issues. His work offered a more polished political-academic rationale for ALMPs than his more bombastic precursors Charles Murray and George Gilder. Reflecting American President Ronald Regan, Mead advocated in his book 'The New Politics of Poverty' that the welfare state's obsession with economic equality was outdated, and that the real problem was 'dependency', that the welfare state enfeebled individuals, taking from their purpose in life. In this, he fed into Regan's formulation of 'government is the problem'. Mead systematically sought to implement, through policy contributions and political activism - authoritarian work-first policies backed with punitive conditional measures to jolt people into any form of paid employment however menial, dirty, or low paid as a necessary prerequisite for escaping poverty (Wacquant, 2009). The significant legacy of his work is to reformulate the welfare state as a political failure and to assert poverty as an moral failing of individuals who are poor-adopting pithy phrases such as 'learned dependency', 'underclass', 'non-working poor' or the 'culture of poverty', to achieve political ambitions. In this formulation reliance on others leads to downward spiral of poverty, incompetence and even criminality. While jobseeking and ALMP are neologisms, this tension between providing support and insisting on behavioural conformity with economic and social norms has an enduring history- present at the origin of Roosevelt's New Deal (Fraser, 1992), aminating the UK's poor laws, the introduction of Bismarckian social insurance and labour exchanges.

Much research explores the governance structures, policy formation and evaluation of ALMPs in different countries (de Graaf et al. 2015). For their proponents, ALMPs are a given, considered as effectively the only option in an austere economic context to expand interventions into the lives of the unemployed, as passive benefits are no considered viable (Bonoli, 2013). Following critics of welfare, ALMPs pose the 'problem' (Baachi, 2015; Demazière & Delpierre, 2020) of unemployment in terms of the individual – requiring training on the 'supply side' of the market if not explicitly blaming claimants. Evocatively, activation policies have been equated to a 'trampoline' rather than the 'safety net' of older

modes of welfare (Giddens, 2013). Critics of activation policies abound, and allege that not only do they push individuals into precarious work, impose cruel psychological punishment, stigmatise individuals, but they are ineffective at reducing unemployment, especially for youths (Hansen and Leschke, 2017; Demazière & Delpierre, 2020; Tyler, 2020).

Our interest here is less in contributing to these debates about the effect or efficacy of these ALMPs, rather it is to surface the tension in welfare systems around the universal treatment of citizens, the differential treatment of those who the state feels needs care; and to frame this tension as it emerges algorithmically in the welfare systems.

2.2.2 Profiling markers and statistical models

The previous section illustrated that while algorithms may be a new development, the logics which underpin and justify them are quite old. This section adds to the previous one by critically examining the politics and practices of datafication, quantification and qualification associated in first generation welfare profiling algorithms. Profiling is the recording and analysing of an individual's behavioural or psychological traits to assist in identifying categories, types or clumps of people. The origin of the term arises from an essentialised outline or reduced drawing, writing or graphing of a person, and captures the subtlety of the concept in being both precise and reduced detail. The starting point for all profiling systems is an individual registering with PES, accomplished by providing information by means of a questionnaire mostly consisting of forced choice, closed or factual questions to surface identity, entitlements and the context of the claim for assistance.

In this datafication process, individuals, with their complex messy lives, flatten their experience, identity and predicament into a simple category that allows the state to administer them. The term datafication captures the transformation of social action into computerised quantified data, which increasingly involves real-time tracking and various approaches to predictive analysis (Mayer-Schoenberger and Cukier, 2013), a social process that has become gradually ever more naturalised (van Dijck, 2014). The term data derives from the Latin term *datum* which literally means *a thing given*. The terms transmission into science comes in the early enlightenment, when natural scientists explores naturally occurring things given by God. Central to this idea is that these things are natural gifts, part of a generous cycle of reciprocity (Malinowski, 1922; Mauss, 1925). In contemporary datafication practices, data does not arise from fundamental gift relations with nature; to collect data is not to receive what is given but to extract what is not (Ingold, 2016).

Although the welfare state is a bureaucratically administered system of gift relations, or mutual commitment, the process of extruding data from people requires that they break off important markers

of selfhood to establish themselves in the world of welfare. For example, identifying into normative binary gender is important, complex elaborations of gender are not. In this way, data snaps apart markers from the currents and entanglements of social life. Datafication enthusiasts tend to assume a self-evident relationship between data and people, which is rooted in the prevailing social norm of statistical science. This relies on a belief in the objectivity of quantification, a seamless transmission from the corporal, biological human into a digital avatar. Of course, what to break off, who does the breaking off, and whether individuals can resist this breaking off are deeply political and cultural questions. So, if the State was truly gender neutral it would not bother asking anyone about their gender to receive unemployment supports. Once something is broken off from the person it can generally become quantitative, hardened, closed off into a fact to be counted. This collection of these pieces broken off, once totalised are renewed as natural, often called "raw data". This raw data is devoid of close up intimate engagements with unemployed people and their rich and vital experiences of being. Rather, raw data and its transformation into Government statistics allows us to look at unemployment from a distance as an objective fact of life that is commonly assumed to be objective, neutral, and indisputable.

In our popular imagination statistics are collected around unemployment. Neutral, passive researchers go out into the world and unproblematically collect and collate descriptions of the natural world. Such assumptions commonly fail to take account of the social and organisational processes involved in the production and dissemination of these important numbers, as well as the performative and reflexive aspects of the statistics. Statistics are political, they render vivid images of society that call for action. Performative in the sense unemployment is not a natural or objective category; it is an organisational category of government and the act of categorising someone as unemployed, more than anything else makes people unemployed. Reflexive in the sense that the statistics of unemployment are consumed crudely by government and individuals, belying the complex issues around how they are produced, and government and individuals make decisions based on the statistics, which in turn impact unemployment statistics. The ubiquity of statistics around unemployment gives a false sense of seeing the actual experience of being unemployed - the model is not the terrain.

Quantifying and 'numberifying' the social is the central technology of modern states, society, science and economy (Woolf 1961; Duncan 1984; Desrosières 1998, 2003; Verrans, 2011 and Diaz-Bone and Didier, 2016). But like all technologies, numbering is not ethically and socially neutral, indeed it changes the very meaning and experience of life. Notwithstanding Kronecker's C.19th injunction that "God made the integers, all the rest is men's work" (Crump 1990; Hawking, 1995), counting is a relatively late human technology, mathematics is normative (Wittgenstein 1964), a cultural accomplishment. For example, use of zero, ubiquitous in computing only took hold in the enlightenment (Whitehead and Russell, 1910), the rise of the metric system arises in the C. 19th (Duncan, 1984 and Alder 2002), the conquering of chronic time (Zerubavel, 1976), and measured-out territory (Dourish, 2015), are all really 19th and 20th century innovations. National statistics, the numbers that are a core technology that links the macro to the micro, the state to the individual, parts to wholes, allowing comparisons and agglomerations that underpin our contemporary political economy and imagination become ubiquitous in the mid twentieth century, just over 70 years ago.

Algorithms, as presently conceived rely of a monist approach to geometry (Serres, 1993), one that relies on Cartesian and Leibnizian universals whilst precludes the pluralism of Cartesian analysis and Leibnizian combination. In practical policy terms, and august debates in the field of mathematics- the algorithmic decision making we find is profoundly antithetical to European pluralist values. The thread of enquiry into the sociology of quantification was present at the beginning of many of these innovations, in Durkheim and Mauss (1903), and Tarde (1949), becoming a distinct field in revulsion to the quantification in the work of Cicourel (1964), Garfinkel (1967) Blumer (1969) and Becker (1972), largely critical of the monopoly of truth from quantum. In parallel the history of science/ socio technical studies (Kuhn, 1962) set off another line of enquiry as science took an epistemological turn ultimately leading to the emergence of Actor-network theory (Latour and Woolgar, 1979) and convention theory Salais & Thévenot 1986). And yet, the very act of developing such elaborate critiques substantiates the monopoly of quantifying and numberifying of the social. And yet, the central concept of the number is largely absent from this line of enquiry, as though numbers are an innocent worldmaking practice.

Curiously, the welfare algorithms orientate towards geographic, demographic, behavioural and psychographic markers of the individual. This echoes an earlier and settled debate in marketing theory on marketing segmentation. Segmentation (along with targeting and positioning in the STP formula) was one of the core planks of marketing theory encapsulating the idea that customers gather, clump and cluster into tribes that have homogenous needs and respond to homogenous stimulation (Kotler, 2009). Similar to the form of profiling used in welfare systems, segmentation can be achieved by clustering approaches, the unsupervised gathering of people who present with similar statistical markets, or by a more artistic, impressionistic human activity of identifying patterns of people. Before segmentation gave way to mass customisation, and segments of one (Blattberg and Deighton, 1991), marketing produced taxonomies of customers based initially on their demographic and geographic markers until people no longer feel into the groove of their place and age, and latterly on psychographic and behavioural markets.

Segmentation works to massify and compound individuals into collections of information about individuals. This works based on equivalence, the claim that people are so alike that they can be combined, compared, added and divided as a singular phenomenon (Martin and Lynch, 2009). The four bases of segmentation foundered as they became less and less useful (Firat and Shultz, 1997) as equivalence came under pressure. This reflected the sense that individuals were no longer as fixed, predictable, and homogenous, and so they did not correspond to each other in table format. A generation before algorithmic welfare, algorithmic segmentation (Dibb and Simkin 1994, Dolnicar and Lazarevski, 2009; Ghaemi, et al, 2009; D'Urso et al, 2015) ran out of patience with multivariate clustering algorithms and reverted to consider segmentation more an analogue artistic practice of market research than a digital science.

All models are a simplified description of the world, into something that is cognitively or technically manageable. There is always a gap between the model and the social world, the map is never the terrain (Korzybski, 1941), the menu is not the meal (Watts, 2010). As René Magritte's "*ceci n'est pas une pipe*" brings our attention to, our symbols for understanding and representing the world, are not the world itself. Within this schema, the gap between model and the reality it aspires to represent is always mediated, in ways that importantly miss things- termed bias; and in ways that are considered irrelevant- termed noise. There is always the greater concern around the extent to which a homogenous population exists, an essential prerequisite for statistical modelling to work (Flyvbjerg, 2020), particularly the form of statistics that rely on regression such as algorithmic welfare. At stake is whether the labour market is complex, and so can be modelled with ever more data and processing power; or whether it is chaotic, random and without order. Complex systems can be conquered with perfect information that when fully understood can allow perfectly accurate predictions of a system, whereas chaotic systems may behave in complex ways, until they do not.

From the raw material of individuals numbered, compounded into datafied clusters emerges narratives that shape meaning as to what this means- data does not stand alone (Dourish and Gómez Cruz, 2018), rather is invited into models. Beyond the issues of producing data, there is considerable symbolic and imaginative effort to make data work (Thornham and Gómez Cruz, 2016) the discursive, operation and material construction that surrounds data to make it self-legitimizing and self-fulfilling. So it is common to discuss the issue of long-term unemployment as having a scarring effect, scarring is an allusion to physical trauma that is variously used in economics, social policy and sociology. Inert data is brought to life as socially significant by narrative (Dourish, 2016, Gillespie, 2011; 2014; Seaver, 2017) that translates (Bolin and Anderson Schwarz, 2015) and framing (Pentzold & Fischer 2017).

We will now examine what these models look like in practice and how they work with reference to examples that are used within PES' day to day activities.

In/Out Models & Poisson Distribution

The In/Out modelling has high suitability to mapping the flow of an individual's activity, for example from being inactive (e.g. a carer) to being employed. As noted in D3.1 micro-data allows for the most accurate scenario for this method. So, for the example above it could map the cause of the individual's inactivity and return to employment (i.e. in receipt of home carers allowance, ages of children,

previous employment, education, income, mortgage, etc..). As such this statistical method could move beyond 'information' and into 'knowledge'. Using a Poisson model to predict flow between the 4 categories would also have some relevance. Poisson distributions are often used to predict seemingly random occurrences, especially clusters. In this theory randomness does not equate to chance and Poisson models are often used to debunk coincidences or luck. They are effective in situations of chaos and can bring order to seemingly coincidental clusters (e.g. Three lottery wins in a small town in one month). While Poisson models do not focus on individual cases (i.e. it cannot predict when person A will get a job) it can show the likelihood of number of individuals moving between each of the 4 categories in the future. Where Poisson could be useful is in determining the number of people who would have moved into employment had they not been subject to interventions such as ALMPs. It would additionally be very strong in assisting with visualising both the supply and demand side of a labour market, which has many unpredictable and chaotic properties.

Logit and Probit Models

This is the primary method of calculation of the PEX algorithm (used in Ireland); and also, within the unemployment processing systems of Austria; Australia; Italy; the Netherlands; Sweden and the United States. Logit and Probit models have a high level of inflexibility as they only use two alternatives Yes/No or 1/0. These types of models work effectively with questionnaires that primarily ask Yes/No style questions (similar to the PEX development questionnaire) or other scenarios where there are only two alternatives. The very obvious problem with using this method is its inflexibility and simplicity and it is difficult to see how it can be applied successfully to a complex situation such as employment that has many individualised variables and scenario or a chaotic system such as a market. It is limited to information and provides little knowledge. It is possible a good choice where there is basic data and where more complex data from multiple sources is not available.

Random Forests and Decision Trees

Random forest and decision trees appear to have an improved ability to predict an outcome based on a greater set of variables. This would indicate that they have potential in allowing predictions for a wide variety of individualised variables concerning moving from unemployment or inactive statuses to employed or self-employed statuses. The issue of overfitting and use on new data is concerning and may limit this method to being used as a development tool to identify variables but not as an active live tool. However, this method, while using statistical calculations, also bridges towards more detailed and specific Decision Support methods for machine learning and AI which are the disruptive technologies that HECAT are aiming to encourage use of in public services.

Gathering and analysing data has traditionally had problems of quantity and being able to visualise and explain certain situations succinctly. For any given situation there is unending amounts of data that can be collected. So, to make it manageable data is sorted and categorised into easy to understand variables. As can be seen in the input data used for many of the PES algorithms and statistical systems the variables selected for analysis differ from system to system. There is most often than not certain standard questions that are asked of subjects (gender, age, marital/co-habitation status) both in the PES systems and in general questionnaires. Grouping individuals into demographics indicates an assumption of similarity in circumstances, needs, etc.

This is a generally accepted way of administering large human datasets. However, in the era of Big Data and increased computing power these categories should not matter. It should be possible to gather every variable and sub variable and provide an individual profile of circumstances, needs and desires around employment. Questionnaires are just one side of the data collection in PES systems, there is also administrative data collected by PES and other agencies. So, in these cases the development of a new platform is limited to the variables and data is available, as is pointed out in D3.1 the quality of the data is important. The disconnect between questionnaires and administrative data and the power of Big Data processing cannot be solved over a short space of time. So the option in developing a new platform is to look at alternative methods of identifying unemployed people who are at risk of remaining unemployed on a long term basis or to radically change the system of

visualisation from that of visualising unemployed people to visualising both the supply and demand sides of the labour market so as to encourage realistic decision making.

Decision Support Systems and AI

The types of decision support discussed in D3.1 are related to systems used to select the most suited candidate for a job. Such tools are widely used by recruitment services and focus largely on individual characteristics. In theory these systems should be an improvement on statistical systems that place information over knowledge and are more focused on individual cases. The various sub-methods used in decision support systems that are outlined in D3.1 have both positive and negative attributes in the development of an ethical algorithm. The most obvious problem with scoring methods is the ease of placing biases on certain attributes. While scoring the relevance of a skill or qualification against a job specification is expected, rating other characteristics of an individual may be problematic, especially where the algorithm or final system is for use by a government for its citizens.

However, AHP method uses a more complex method for scoring attributes which may reduce bias at the design stage by introducing alternatives. Data, and its method of collection, is an issue with this method as many of the attributes of an individual are not recorded in administrative data. Skills such as leadership, problem solving, language, teamwork must be either self-declared or judged as part of a psychological personality test. The ambiguous nature of personality tests and self-declaration has the possibility to create errors due to the established criticisms of these tests (e.g. aiming to game the test based on what a candidate thinks is required rather than as a true reflection). As many of these systems are focused solely on one side of the labour market and recruitment, they are limited in being able to visualise the whole of the labour market. These types of algorithms have benefits and perhaps would be beneficial if used as part of a more encompassing system. A more complex system of automated decision making would benefit as it increases the numbers of attributes on a tree for individuals and could dilute any inherent biases towards certain attributes. If these systems become pervasive for company hiring, it is also important to understand how they operate so as to surface their biases and possibly include measures in the HECAT system that can assist a candidate in overcoming these biases. These systems could additionally be useful if the HECAT system was to be expanded to include opportunities for training and education so that an individual could match their skills with their employment expectations (i.e. individual perceived job quality metrics – location, pay, career progression, stability).

Labour Flow

Labour flow modelling represents calculations and visualisations that are a closer match to the aims of the HECAT project, ethics, tools, and a supply/demand labour market visualisation. There appear to be many positives to these models including focusing on the interconnections between employing organisations and the labour market as a cluster. This leans towards being able to provide a broad underlying system that can be tailored between countries and additionally between regions in a country. There is less chance of bias in the calculations as focus moves away from the individual in the first instance towards the liquidity of the labour market. There also appears to be a desire to keep data simple and uncomplicated when mapping networks. Models which focus primarily on the individual and their skills or characteristics would need to gather data on large numbers of disparate variables that are often very personal to individuals.

There is a danger that the data feeding some of these models is limited, such as using data from LinkedIn which may result in certain segments of the labour market being excluded, and most likely the most vulnerable participants in the labour market (e.g. those whose economic circumstances limit their ability to access the internet and, as such, LinkedIn). As a public service algorithm or system all levels of the labour market need to be considered.

Returning to one of the key drivers of the PEX algorithm – to find a way to best use the resources of the PES – the Italian experience in the region of Friuli (4.7) using social network analysis reminds us that it is important to focus any assistance on those who will find it more difficult to secure employment and that there is a need to recognise social capital along with qualifications and skills in providing a system that is useful for both citizen and PES stakeholders. The usefulness of a decision

support system will be different if you are PES (e.g. reduce spend on unemployment, increase economic activity) or a citizen (e.g. support for living expenses while unemployed, finding a suitable job based on personal criteria).

Discussion

The underplayed desire to profile arises in the limited capacity and flexibility of PES to service clients. The need to profile is an affordance of most PES's fixed capacity. The OECD recommend sustaining the ratio of caseworker to unemployed people at 1:150, but employment in most countries rises to 15%+ during times of economic hardship and can drop to 3-5% at times. Certainly, within a European public sector context it is not possible to rapidly modulate service provision to sustain PES service provision at a 1:150 ratio, and this creates pressure to ration services. Thus, rather than maintain universal service provision and modulate the extent of effort, rationing profiling is introduced. Given the lag time for deploying such systems, they often arrive after the necessity for them has abated. Encoded into profiling techniques are thresholds to generate a segment of those who need additional services in and around the fixed capacity of PES.

Slovenian Employment numbers change; but there is an aspiration to sustain PES caseworkers fixed at a ratio of 1:150

Profiling systems of any type are always problematic but one generated by an algorithm to assign a 'score' to a human individual inevitably raises questions of algorithmic bias, especially so when it is a government deploying an algorithm to ration resources to citizens. Were they to work as envisaged, at the heart of these various PES projects is an ambition to positively discriminate against those who are likely to thrive in the labour market without intervention. The attraction to algorithmic profiling is that it dehumanises the discrimination, eliding personal responsibility, thereby throwing the unpleasant business of sorting citizens into a black box. Using probabilistic causation around existing discrimination within the labour market, gives rise to natural justice concerns around formally encoding discriminatory practices, echoing, or even amplifying them.

Designed often removed certain characteristics from the final models either to simplify the processing or for political reasons such as selecting a marker that is too sensitive. The little evaluative research done on algorithmic profiling has explored its functional qualities – effectiveness, compliance, and consequences. Nor has there been much in the way of concern over the prurient nature of the questions on the profiling questionnaires. This lack of curiosity might reflect the poor general literacy around how such algorithms work. For many non-mathematicians who seek them out it is easy to understand what they do on the surface – their purpose, their actions, their consequences – but rarely their inner workings, networks of dependence and independence or their mathematical nuances. Despite this, the profiling algorithm passed into usage with minimal fuss or examination by third parties.

2.2.3 Profiling markers and a fraying social compact

Previous sections have reviewed the ethical, social, and technical dimensions of algorithmic profiling from a sociological and anthropological perspective. This final section will draw together and parse the hidden theological influences that have had an impact on the development of unemployment and the algorithms created to manage it.

Broadly the various algorithms separate those who the PES perceive will to be frictionally unemployed and will quickly find new work and those who require additional supports, ALMPs to governmentalise the unemployed into jobseekers (Boland and Griffin, 2015). Unemployment welfare is an anti-revolutionary construct (Ewald, 2020), that moderates the impact of absolute poverty to moderate social unrest to a level at which the State's existence is made durable. This understanding follows on from Machiavelli's formulation on how political continuity is insured through internal stability (Berlin, 1974). In Machiavelli's *Florentine Histories*, he analytically considers the Ciompi Revolt (1378), an insurrection and then revolution led by a union of the poorest working class in Florence; for a brief period the elite were overthrown and a radical democracy reigned. Machiavelli retells the story as an instructive parable of how an unchecked abundance of poverty spills over into political violence-costing the Medici their position temporarily.

It is this lesson from medieval peasant rebellions that animated the 'Birth of the Welfare State' in the post-war era as an attempt to produce an enduring global peace, an end of history (Fukuyama, 1992). Stirring these policy motivations are debates about the end of work in a post work 4th industrial revolution; a generations-old political anxiety (Gorz, 1999; Graeber, 2013; Fleming, 2015) and the political problem of administering a society based on work, without work. Unemployment welfare is at least the state can do to moderate an excess of inequality (Pickett and Wilkinson, 2010; Picketty, 2020); it is a calibrated response to do enough to keep people off the streets, and welfare is a pacification technology to preserve the status quo of wealth and power.

The current era of intense welfare reform (Esping-Andersen, 2002) formed in the Scandinavian moral economy of responsabilisation and activation, took hold in the USA under Regan and Clinton, in Germany with the Hartz reforms, France's Sarkozy, and in Britain from Thatcher, Blair and Cameron. Yet, these reforms are just as political as revolutions, seeking to transform society in line with ideal horizons: not a revolutionary apocalypse, but an earthly 'City of God' where individuals are tested, judged and reformed (Augustine, 2009). In Esping-Andersen (1990) formulation of three 'worlds of welfare', based on the Catholic, Lutheran and Calvinist religious traditions, the its associated 'punitive turn' (Wacquant, 2012) is a stridently Calvinist instinct, that now dominates the global policy imagination. Calvinists formulations assert that 'poverty was predestined and that the poor are responsible for their plight' (Kahl, 2005: 117). The term 'reformation' immediately invokes the Protestant reformation of Luther, Calvin, Knox and the puritans who cleaved the Roman Catholic Church into a number of reformed churches. However, 'reform' has a much longer history— most evidently in the 'reformatio' of Pope Gregory VII (1073–85), but also throughout the fifteenth century with Christian scholars such as Desiderius Erasmus, John Colet and Thomas More and others. The urge towards reformation is not simply Calvinist, nor Protestant instinct; it suffuses the Christian and Jewish tradition. Indeed, the transformation from the pantheon of Gods of Egyptian, Greek and Pre-Christian Rome, from polytheism to monotheism, is also a transformation in the interests of God unto reforming man's conduct. Ancient Israelite prophecy – from Amos, Isaiah, Ezekiel to Jeremiah – was not just an excoriating critique of society, but also a demand for reform, of rulers, priests and ordinary people. Thus, the impulse to reform appears to emerge from the 'world-image' of Judaism and Christianity; life as a trial of redemption set by God for the chosen people or each person.

In the separation of those to be reformed, and those who can recover work themselves, the policy machinery of 'reform' is considered 'apolitical' and 'areligious', as though state interventions were a

purely scientific, disinterested, evidence-based governance of society in order to optimise individual and collective life – and always in balance with individual choice.

This model traces the bureaucratic rationalities and anxieties around judgement (Weber, 1922; Bauman, 1989; DuGay, 2000) that leads to Government's depersonalising the act of discriminating to a formula. These rationalities auger the algorithmic authority (Lustig & Nardi, 2015) that can then take action in the world (Lipsky, 1983) through inscrutable ALMPS, that have delivered an era of ever tougher and more elaborate state control over the economy and the individual, which in their extreme variety, traduce commitments to social democratic principles of social equality and active parliamentary democracy. Labour market algorithms represent the state-in-action (Ungerson, 2003; Lister, 2003) at the point of care of vulnerable citizens with entitlements (Jenson & Saint-Martin, 2003; Taylor-Gooby, 2004; Pfau-Effinger, 2005), and so are beyond public-good, public-sphere or public-concern algorithms (Bunz, 2014). With such tremendous agency in vulnerable people's lives, these algorithms demonstrate how "authority is being increasingly expressed algorithmically" (Pasquale, 2015, p. 8) to tinker with people and democracy. Unresolved is whether such algorithms have any place in the main engine room of European social solidarity.

Beyond this, there is a deeper consideration of the rationalities and logics that animate how a democracy, the public realm and the state adopt these mathematical-digital technologies to administer, govern and construct welfare and care. As we plunge ethnographically into the world of the algorithm, we necessarily encounter the moral and ethical foundations encoded into the objective, cold, and absurdist formula. Going further, we explore the telos of calculability (inspired by Callon, 1988) that digital knowledge produces in theological terms as a new iteration of purgatory.

Buried in and around the objectivity of the formula is a deep cultural code of work as a vocation and capitalist enterprise - as the grace of god (Weber, 1958) and the hand of providence or the hand of the market (Agamben, 2011). Furthermore, poverty, unemployment and jobseeking can be interpreted as a purgatory on earth, an edifying punishment to purge sins (especially sloth & pride). This journey of unemployment, not unlike Dante's (1308-1320) in the Divine Comedy, begins with judgement, as penitents are directed along a path and must yield to the assistance of their guides in order to make them suitable to re-enter the labour market. In suggesting such a radical interpretation, we aspire to expand the vista of ethnographic inquiry into imagined logics of the tecnotopias from which bureaucratic sorting algorithms emerge. In short, PES algorithms have curious theologies, which continue to exert an influence that is the more powerful because it goes unacknowledged.

3.0 Case histories of algorithms in PES

A brief history

First-generation algorithms have been in use since 1994 and 1995 in Australia and the US, respectively and across European countries from the late 1990s onwards (O'Connell et al., 2009). Individual countries have unique historical genealogies of social welfare schemes and, as such, developments often occur locally rather than pan-European. However, there is considerable cross-fertilisation of policy measures between countries led by the OECD, EU, IMF and Worldbank (Beblavý et al., 2015). Indeed, the very concept of unemployment is a globalised administrative and statistical construct, echoing out from municipal social insurance schemes of the late industrial revolution. The construct became increasingly institutionally firm after the creation of International Labour Organisation (ILO) under the Versailles settlement of the Great War (1914-1918) and developed into the fixed definition we now recognise. Nonetheless, there are also significant historical, political, economic and social developments across countries which foster different understandings of how welfare should be administered, who should receive it and how much they should receive (Esping-Andersen, 1990). These different European understandings echo Huntington's clash of civilisation thesis (1993).

Despite moves towards the incorporation of algorithmic practices, there are few successes or attempts at harmonisation of systems across the EU. Indeed, while the technology has gained in popularity, a development driven by increasing labour market volatility, it has failed to reach what can be described as incumbent status. Some examples follow which make it clear that there are both convergences and divergences in how PES organisations across the EU view best practice for achieving their goals.

- **The UK** was an early adopter of statistical profiling but subsequently dropped it as an all-encompassing system over dual concerns with accuracy and operational effectiveness (O'Connell et al., 2009).
- **Denmark's** Job Barometer model was created using administrative data on the entire inflow into unemployment from January 1999 to June 2003 and used a duration model to calculate the probability of finding employment within the next six months (Rosholm/Hammer, 2004). Due to large amounts of paperwork and being time-heavy, it is being phased out (Larsen/Jonsson, 2011) and a new statistical profiling tool is being developed, particularly aimed at youth unemployment (Madsen, 2015).
- **Finland's** Statistical Profiling Tool, introduced in 2007, is considered one of the most successful models. A logit model, it predicted the probability of long term unemployment and categorised jobseekers into low-risk or high-risk of long-term unemployment (Riipinen, 2011). This tool was assessed soon after deployment as being highly efficient, with 89% accuracy. Despite this, caseworker-resistance to the tool has resulted in problems with implementation (Riipinen, 2011).
- **Sweden's** Assessment Support Tool (AST), introduced in 2011, is a combination of an algorithm and caseworker input and uses a probit model to estimate the probability of becoming long-term unemployed (6 months) through 11 predictors (Loxha/Morgandi, 2014).
- **The Netherland's** Work Profiler was introduced in 2014; it is a logit model that calculates the jobseeker's probability of returning to the labour market within a year but lacks mathematical robustness as it assesses clients nationwide based on 2008/2009 data on unemployed persons in the Province of North Holland (Wijnhoven/Havinga, 2014).
- **Poland** (Niklas et al., 2015), **Croatia** –StAP (Croatian Employment Services (CES), 2018) and **Germany** –TrEffeR (German Federal Employment Agency (FEA), 2016) are also exploring methods of calculable assessments of unemployed people. The danger with these experiments is that they lose any potential for harnessing the power of new (big) data, dynamic algorithms and machine learning to provide effective solutions. Instead, they become a mechanistic process of sorting and stigmatising (Tyler, 2019).

3.1 Case Examples

The current section outlines five individual case studies of statistical profiling in Ireland, Croatia, Austria, France, and Australia. The case countries were selected on a pragmatic basis as there is a lack of available data on the design, implementation, and function of European statistical profiling tools. The five cases selected were those which offered the richest data sources. The case studies offer a rich contextual background to the implementation of each tool, drawing out key features of the design and ambitions of each tool and briefly reflecting on the core issues which surround the individual countries' experiences of statistical profiling. Whilst the individual cases display diversity in the types of tools deployed and varying levels of success with their implementation, a number of common threads highlighted in the final remarks of section two of the current report are apparent in the individual case studies. These issues include difficulty with implementation and concern with the accuracy, appropriateness and ethics of the data employed to build the tools and these are some of the core issues which will form the backbone of section four of the current report.

Context and background

In the immediate aftermath of the 2008 global financial crisis, the Irish economy endured growth in unemployment from 4.6% to 15.9%. The sovereign debt crisis which followed the banking crisis led to an IMF/EU bailout, creating a context where the Irish government needed to restore the Irish economy in the eyes of international lenders. The dual crisis led to a significant appetite for labour market reforms (Hick, 2018), including the introduction of a profiling algorithm- PEX used to ration access to active labour market interventions. The PEX algorithm is part of a much larger, radical transformation of the Irish social welfare system. Before 2012, against the international norm, Irish welfare policy was strongly passive- in that unemployed people were left to their own devices with a basic payment to prevent absolute poverty. Since the early 1980s, the OECD has chided various Irish governments for their 'generous', 'lax' and 'passive' policies. Against the backdrop of the deep recession, economic crisis and Troika (IMF-EC-ECB) bailout, a programme of radical welfare reform (Pathways to Work, 2012) that introduced highly active labour market policies (ALMP) such as mandatory training, supports, participation girded by the threat of sanctions and conditionality (Boland and Griffin, 2015).

PEX was introduced in 2012 to the everyday work practices of Ireland's one-stop-shop unemployment centres called 'Intreo offices'. *The study underpinning the algorithm was reported in the document National Profiling of the Unemployed in Ireland in July 2009, was based on 2006 survey data collected from 30,762 individuals in two cities (Galway and Waterford) and was deployed within the PES in 2011* (O'Connell, et al., 2009). The ambition of PEX was to identify individuals at risk of long-term unemployment and ensure they would "no longer remain on the Live Register for lengthy periods without an appropriate offer of assistance from the state" (Government of Ireland, 2012, p. 5). As part of this reassessment of the provision of social welfare services the Job Path scheme was introduced which makes use of contracted external service providers to assist in finding employment or further training opportunities for those who are long term unemployed (12months +) or are at risk by having a PEX score of 5% or less (Department of Social Protection, 2013). This scheme involves attending meetings with the service provider for a defined period where a personal plan is developed to assist in finding employment. In practice, many caseworkers set aside PEX scores if they do not make sense to them, or they refuse to determine PEX scores if they perceive it to produce an unfavourable outcome for the applicant. Referral to additional supports increases the likelihood of being sanctioned (withdrawal of part or all of a social welfare payment), and a considerable loss of agency and autonomy in job search.

Inside PEX

Against the backdrop of restoring prudent management of the national finances, PEX has an important political-economic marketing function in Irish statecraft. This belies the relative simplicity of the algorithm from our reverse-engineered reproduction (we were denied access to the actual algorithm). The data collection that informed the algorithm was based on three months of fieldwork in 2006 with 30,762 people who received either Jobseekers Benefit and/or Jobseekers Allowance who were tracked for a period of 78 weeks. Questions were asked around several categories such as; Perceived Health, Spousal Earnings, Employment/Unemployment History, Willingness to Relocate, Location, Transport and Education History. Having controlled for the predictive capacity of over 120 explanatory variables, the final PEX algorithm is based on 26 characteristics.

The PEX algorithm controlled for the predictive capacity of over 120 explanatory variables, whittled down to 26 characteristics such as a recent history of long-term unemployment, advanced age, number of children, relatively low levels of education, literacy/numeracy problems, location in urban areas, lack of personal transport, low rates of recent labour market engagement, and spousal earnings. Some variables such as membership of an ethnic minority and marital status were considered statistically significant for inclusion but were excluded as they were perceived as being overly discriminatory and perhaps even in breach of GDPR and anti-discrimination law. Curiously there are two algorithms, one for male and one for female and with three classifications (low, medium, high) in each based on an individual's probability of leaving the live register within 12 months. The PEX score aimed to allow subsequent intervention from caseworkers to be informed by this classification with more assistance given to those with the lowest probability of exit.

The 2009 study, National Profiling of the Unemployed in Ireland, was considered by the authors as a pilot, and they were taken aback when no further updating of the algorithm was undertaken. A more recent study, Predicting the Probability of Long-Term Unemployment Using Administrative Data (McGuinness, et al., 2014), was issued in June 2014. This report notes the age of the data that developed PEX and essentially carries out an audit of it and subsequently recommends that a Labour Market Disadvantage Model (LMD) may be more suited to current labour market conditions. The current algorithm's design is based on data from a period of economic stability in the years before the 2008 economic crash and subsequent recession. When introduced, the tool had an efficacy of around 77% (in 2012), dropping to around 60% in 2017 and is now likely to be no better 50%. A 2019 review (ERSI, 2019) also surfaced the problem of missing data and coding errors in the profiling questions, as well as little statistical difference between treatment offices that used the full suite of Intreo tools and control offices - this was understood to be related to the geographic context of the office.

Towards understanding PEX

Initial observations of the PEX algorithm and its use by the DSP point to it becoming a singular tool that can be held up as an untouchable 'magical algorithm' of governmentality. While it is transparent and available for study, probably, the vast majority of those to whom it will be applied will never question its validity. Leading, then, perhaps to PEX becoming a "powering" device aimed at categorising unemployed people and a convenient defence for any questioning of the current social welfare processes. Similar to Hick's observations of passing the buck and pointing the finger at the Troika to explain away and defend the austerity imposed by Irish Governments (Hick, 2018) and Lustig and Nardi's "algorithmic authority" (2015, p. 743) over humans as well as technology. There is little, within the current discourse of social welfare politics, to suggest that the DSP is interested in the ongoing validity of PEX. In a type of 'cargo cult science,' the DSP are building systems that have the appearance of robust action and which they foresee as reducing long term unemployment but are, at the same time, adding actors into an increasingly complex set of networks that have the effect of removing their body from direct responsibility for their 'clients'. The consequences of these moves are now becoming apparent, and it is these consequences that drive interest in the social reality of the PEX algorithm. Michel Serres (2013) subtly contrasts between computers which simulate algorithms and the long-exiled algorithmic thinking that these computers have traduced. The PEX algorithm, like all contemporary algorithms, relies on Cartesian universals- the notion that individual phenomena are instantiations of general universal laws. The passage from the local to the universal is, therefore, for

the Cartesian, relatively straightforward: one must simply find and declare these laws and hope that one has not missed something. Such a mode of thinking is monist, seeing an unproblematic singular relation between the local and the universal. Serres, in *Les Origines de la géométrie* (1993), directs us to explore Leibniz more pluralist combinations which act less as a transcendental condition of isomorphism and more as a procedural operator that generates local instances of order without any necessary sense of a pre-existing grand unity. As the sands of time and society shift under the PEX algorithm rendering it irrelevant, Serres rediscovery of ancient Egypt and Babylon algorithmic thought by way of in the seventeenth century Pascal and Leibniz rekindled interest in this alternative way of reasoning that privilege calculation, performing a series of operations rather than trying to demonstrate that a particular axiom holds.

3.3 Austria AMAS

Context and background

The Public Employment Service of Austria (AMS) commissioned a feasibility study in 2016 to assess the chances of different groups of unemployed people in the Austrian labour market to find work. Similarly to the Irish PEX model, this work was begun at a time of socio-economic urgency when the Austrian rate of unemployment was steadily increasing from a low in 2011 of 4.56% (EU average ~11%) to 6.01% in 2016 (EU average 7.8%), with no signs of slowing down. It was not clear at the time, but this would in-fact be the peak of Austrian unemployment, it has since decreased to its present rate of 4.78%, closer in line to its pre-recession rate, and meeting several international standards of full employment (often pegged around 5%). However, the COVID-19 pandemic is likely to impact this in the near term.

Nevertheless, the work was started, and analysis was delegated to Synthesis Forschung, an independent contractor hired by the Austrian government at an initial cost of €240,000. Three years later (in 2019) their analysis was finished and concluded that in line with international best practice that a high accuracy rate could be maintained by sorting unemployed people into three groups (likely / somewhat likely/unlikely to find work). This led to the design of a test algorithm, dubbed AMAS, which was piloted throughout 2019 and 2020, full implementation of the algorithm is anticipated in early 2021.

Inside AMAS

AMAS predominately takes administrative and survey data to produce its analytic conclusions, though the caseworker also has access to the labour market history and hard skills of the unemployed person in question. This data is fed into an algorithm which produces a percentile value (%) based on the attributes and characteristics of the person in question, and which is represented to the caseworker as their "chance of integration" (IC) score. This refers to their chances of being integrated into the labour market. The IC score is then used to sort the unemployed into one of the three groups. The statistical technique used is logistic regression, and AMAS boasts an accuracy rate of between 80% and 85%.

The AMAS profiling algorithm uses many of the internationally standard socio-economic variables which help to classify unemployed people by separating them into three discrete categories.

- Group A – likely to find work in the short term (7 months)
- Group B – unlikely to find work in the short term (longer than 7, but not as long as 24 months)
- Group C – unlikely to find work in the long term (24 months)

As is the case with other similar algorithms, most of the attention of the algorithm and, indeed, the caseworkers who use them is directed towards group C, as this group needs the most help, and will be the recipient of the greatest number of interventions. Group B is also a cause for concern, as there is a sense of urgency that they should receive some interventions to prevent long-term unemployment. Group A requires few if any interventions. The interventions applied generally fall under the heading of "retraining", with group C requiring some kind of retraining to have skills which are useful to the labour market, and group B being flagged as a possibility for retraining. There is also a facility for group C to be discharged to other state services (e.g. addiction treatment).

In addition to the normal suite of socio-economic variables, AMAS incorporates a range of other data sources. These include labour market history; any hard skills possessed by the client; and regional labour market information. These first two are generated through questionnaires completed by the client, and the third through the AMAS database. In this context, labour market history will include the client's work history, including any previous periods of unemployment; previous instances of long-term unemployment (~24 months) are flagged as a potential issue. This labour market history is very detailed, as it includes not only all previous work, but also the duration and intensity of that work, i.e. number of hours worked per day, and if that work was likely to create fatigue, either physical or mental. Hard skills conform to international standards and include reading, writing, capacity to use a computer and the internet etc. Regional labour market information breaks Austria up into its component regions and examines each one as a discrete case that is treated as having its own internal labour market, and this helps caseworkers to tailor their advice and interventions to local circumstances.

AMAS is marketed as a 'supportive tool', which is intended to be used by the caseworker to help them make better judgements and discretionary choices by giving them relevant and timely information. For example, it would be a waste of time for a caseworker to invest many interventions and resources on someone who has been sorted into category A. However, as it is a tool that has a human override, caseworkers are encouraged to use their own intuition and decision-making process if they believe that the algorithm has provided a result that is incorrect.

The controversy surrounding the Implementation of AMAS

This algorithm has been the source of some public backlash, however, due to its inclusion of certain attributes and characteristics which are often excluded from algorithms because they are discriminatory. These include gender, dis(ability) status, and ethnic descent, which were intended to provide caseworkers with an accurate picture of the discriminatory capacities of the labour market. Gender, for example, reduces the prospects of finding a job by 0.14 (14%) for women, and an unusual variable labelled 'obligation of care' was also introduced but was applied only to women. The issue, of course, is that even if this does give us an accurate picture of discrimination in the labour market, that it has a chance of reproducing these biases by reifying them and making it seem as though women are less motivated to find work than men who are otherwise comparable.

These decisions were defended by the president of AMS, who said that the inclusion of these variables accurately represents the "harsh reality" of the labour market. These controversies have delayed the full deployment of the AMAS algorithm, which was originally scheduled for implementation in 2020, but this has now been delayed until 2021. Use of the algorithm will be mandatory for all newly processed unemployed people, though as stated earlier caseworkers are free to accept, modify or dismiss the information provided by the algorithm as they see fit.

3.4 Croatia StAP

Context and background

Croatia's statistically assisted profiling (StAP) was piloted in 2016/17, against the backdrop of persistently higher unemployment than the European average- 9.7% in 2017 compared with an EU average of 7.8%; the fourth highest in the block. The broad impetus for the initiative arose from the noticeably higher rates of long-term unemployment, with significant regional variation, which prompted strategic questions around the effectiveness of Croatia's PES the HZZ (Hrvatski zavod za zaposljavanje). More specifically, the stated rationale to introduce profiling was the high average caseload at HZZ — with 644 cases per counsellor (HZZ, 2018) which is on the high end compared to the public employment services in other member states, and significantly above the OECD recommended norm of 150. A common feature across our case countries thus far is that the implementation has been driven by a general crisis of employment.

Croatia's response to its high rate of unemployment and high ratio of counsellors to clients involved the implementation of energetic ALMP's designed to cycle clients back into employment as quickly as

possible via a mixed system that involves both counsellors and the StAP profiling tool. Profiling was introduced along with other efforts to strengthen existing ALMP provisions, such as more emphasis on individual assessment, personal guidance, the introduction of motivational measures and conditionality to ensure individuals were actively seeking work. Upon registering with HZZ as unemployed, a client will have their first meeting with a counsellor within 15 days. This initial meeting informs the clients of their rights and responsibilities, in addition to what HZZ expects of them. Their primary responsibility is to be active in their own job search efforts, with the first step being to produce an individual action plan (IAP) within 60 days of registration. The IAP is detailed and includes desired employment, as well as any training, qualifications, or education the client will need to achieve their goal. IAP's are supplemented by assessments through individual (questionnaires, interviews) and group work. Tools for assessment include psychological diagnostics (behaviour, attitudes, competences, motivation); structured interview (assessment of individual needs and motivations); guidance (planning activities in order to prevent clients from entering long-term unemployment status). These assessments are completed within the first 60 days. Once the IAP is in place, clients must show evidence that they are adhering to it by writing or updating their CV; documenting their activities in a job search diary; ensuring they communicate with their counsellor; applying for relevant jobs, or seeking the education and training outlined in the IAP. A client meets with their counsellor on a face-to-face basis every 12 weeks, the IAP is reviewed, and any relevant updates or changes are made, which in turn, inform what happens in the next meeting.

Inside StAP

The parameters of the StAP model have been estimated based on registry data from 970,000 unemployment register entries during the 2012-2014 period. Whilst the HZZ database has records of 5.5 million unemployment episodes over 12 years, structural, cyclical, and institutional changes constrained the development to 20% of the available data and time horizon. The aspirational outcome of StAP is to segment the stock of the unemployed based on their likelihood of gaining employment within 12 months. Beyond this, the probability model was designed to identify four outcomes:

- High employment probability within the next 12 months
- No specific indications of employment probability
- Low employment probability within the next 12 months
- Very low employment probability within the next 12 months

Predictors used in the model are human capital (educational attainment and previous work experience), employment and unemployment records (previous entries in the unemployment register, time since last entry and the reason for employment contract termination), specific vulnerable groups (persons with disabilities, war veterans, age), and economic sector (occupation, last employer's economic activity, field of education).

The model incorporates regional labour market differences in Croatia; therefore, the probability of long-term unemployment is also adjusted to the specific labour market characteristics of the area where the unemployed registered people are based. Specific activities, as well as specific active labour market measures for the long-term unemployed, are then planned on the results of the probability estimated through the StAP test. Most recently, it was reported as having a "solid predictive performance of 69% correctly classified" (TAIPEX, 2020). Essentially meaning that the goal of the algorithm is to predict which unemployed people will slip into long-term unemployment, and it can predict this in 69% of cases.

As this tool is used on a supplementary basis, the counsellor has the option to change which category the client falls into. If a client fails to show up for their meetings, does not apply for jobs, or has motivational, health, or social issues then they can be reclassified and put in one of the other categories. According to HZZ the most experienced counsellors rely on their knowledge, intuition and judgement over the outcomes generated by StAP, with less experienced counsellors leaning more heavily on the StAP categories.

StAP and Conditionality

In addition to supplementing the judgement of their counsellors, StAP has other goals which are similar to those of other algorithmic profiling systems. The others are:

- To tailor services to the needs of the client's aspirations and needs.
- To reduce the need for direct contact between counsellors and clients (especially due to the high caseload of counsellors).
- To allow counsellors to spend more time with those clients that need it.

StAP also facilitates deregistration. If an unemployed person fails to find a job within 12 months, they will lapse into the 'inactive' category, and though they will continue to be classified as unemployed, they will no longer receive a social transfer payment. In addition, StAP also deregisters people automatically if they fail to meet certain conditions, for example, missing several meetings with your counsellor in a row is likely to lead to automatic deregistration. This is accompanied by a stipulation that unemployed people will not be able to reregister for at least six months.

It is, therefore, a profiling system with a strong conditionality approach, as also seen in the UK and Ireland, i.e. that the continued provision of unemployment benefits is contingent upon the unemployed person's regular participation with the activities outlined by the PES. It, therefore, seems questionable to describe these people as customers or clients, as they are neither. There are no alternatives for the unemployed person, who must perform to these expectations, and participate in the activities mandated by the PES.

However, a report from 2019 recommended that this practice of deregistration be discontinued, as deregistration reduces the motivation and drive of unemployed people to seek work. Instead, unemployed people who would normally be deregistered will be cited for motivational activities, and counsellors began training in 2018 to offer these motivational activities. It is still too soon to tell if these changes will have the desired impact of decreasing long-term unemployment, but at the very least they do seem more ethical, moral and are more in line with European values than the previous system.

3.5 France Intelligence Emploi

Context and background

France's national employment agency, *pôle emploi* received €20m in 2019 to develop a sophisticated and ultramodern artificial intelligence profiling tool called *intelligence emploi*. The goals of this profiling tool are threefold:

1. Accelerate the return of unemployed people to sustainable employment.
2. Help entrepreneurs find appropriate candidates to fill their vacancies.
3. Automate the process of casework (e.g. by automatically sending emails).

This comes in the context of a relatively recent merger between ANPE and ASSEDIC, two French governmental agencies which were responsible for providing counselling to the unemployed (ANPE) and for distributing welfare payments (ASSEDIC). This merger took place in 2009, and there are still legacy issues which are being worked out, as each organisation had its own interior workplace culture and means of organisation (not only of staff but also of files and data storage). *Intelligence emploi* is intended to be a step forward in solving lingering legacy issues.

Unlike other countries, France was not spurred to create intelligence emploi by a particular rise or crisis in the level of unemployment, which stood last year (2019) at 8.43% (EU average 6.7%). France has wrestled with issues of long-term unemployment for several decades, and it is this trend that is being responded to, rather than recent increases or decreases in the rate of unemployment.

Inside Intelligence Emploi

Both this new artificial intelligence system and the fund which is supporting it are referred to as intelligence emploi (intelligent employment). One of the key motivating factors underpinning its development is data collected by pôle emploi on the subjective perceptions of jobseekers' success by self-evaluation. Jobseekers tend to overrate their likelihood of finding a job, relative to the reality, with most jobseekers estimating that they have between a 50% and 100% chance of finding a job within six months, with the true accuracy being about half of this. After six months, their chances deteriorate at an accelerated rate.

Unlike many other countries, there was a period of in-depth statistical testing where the three most popular ALMP statistical techniques were evaluated by being used on real data. These were then scored on a scale of 1 (weakest), and 4 (strongest) relative to the factors considered most important by pôle emploi:

	Logistic Regression	Random Forest	Neural Network
Predictive Power	2 / 4	3 / 4	4 / 4
Explicability	4 / 4	3 / 4	2 / 4
Pre-processing	2 / 4	3 / 4	4 / 4
Maintainability	1 / 4	2 / 4	3 / 4
Total	9 / 16	11 / 16	13 / 16

Logistic regression (LOGIT) stands out as the weakest of the three techniques examined; it is also the simplest as it estimates the relationship between a binary dependent variable and several independent variables, e.g. what is the likelihood of a person being long term unemployed considering their skills/age/education/region (etc.). This method was found to have middling predictive power and pre-processing capabilities and weak maintainability. Its unusually strong explicability somewhat offsets this. Essentially this means that it provides a good explanation between relationships, such as an association between poverty and unemployment (explicability), but what should be done with this information in practice is not clear (poor predictive power). LOGIT also requires a large amount of pre-processing, and is difficult to maintain, meaning that for even a middling level of predictive power to be maintained that the data sources must be continually updated and curated, requiring constant human intervention.

Random forest modelling uses complex decision trees to predict the value of a dependent variable from multiple independent variables. This can be thought of as a series of if-then statements, e.g. if you are unemployed for three months then you must receive additional counselling if you refuse this counselling, then you will be sanctioned, if you are sanctioned, then you must explain why you refused the counselling (and so on). But this tree has multiple branches, and the person could go the opposite way, e.g. if you accept the counselling, then you will receive access to other allowances/training opportunities. The decision tree will then evaluate which branches tend to lead to employment.

Decision trees suffer from the overfitting problem, where a tree can become too complex and possess too many branches to be useful in practice. Random forest modelling can solve this somewhat by overlaying multiple decision trees onto the data at random, and this discovers the path of least resistance by using training data to discover a smaller number of trees which are the most useful. However, as pôle emploi discovered, though random forest modelling is superior to regression, it also suffers from issues of maintainability, as decision tree models do not accommodate new data sets well unless they have received extensive testing.

Pôle emploi found that neural networks worked the best on their training data. This uses multiple algorithms which overlap with one another in an attempt to replicate the reasoning, interpretive power, and forward planning of a human brain, with mixed results that in many ways are the opposite of the LOGIT results. LOGIT provides an excellent explanation for why two variables are related, but it is unclear what predictive power this has for the future; neural networks offer excellent predictive power, but it is often not clear how or why the algorithms have related certain attributes or characteristics together. This is in addition to its other functions, automatically replying to low-priority or simple email queries, or automatically scanning job seekers' CV's and analysing them relative to all the other CV's it has previously scanned. Intelligence emploi then is a tool which is intended to save time for the caseworkers, who must ration their care and attention so that they can focus on those job seekers in need of their help, but how effective this tool will be in practice remains to be seen.

New Goals and new technology

Many European statistical profiling tools, such as the Irish and Croatian models, are guided by a work first approach which has little regard for the quality or sustainability of employment and often employs sanctions for those who fail to enter the labour market in a timely fashion. Unlike these approaches, the French have opted to develop a tool which has the primary goal of accelerating people's return to **sustainable** employment. Whilst this more ambitious task puts considerable strain on the algorithm, it is none the less a step in the right direction for the use of big data and statistical profiling.

The term artificial intelligence was used deliberately, as the goal is for intelligence emploi to 'learn' from the data which is input so that over time it can make automated decisions which are as good as, or better than a human. At the time of writing this level of artificial intelligence is not realistic, but there are specific goals set out by Pôle emploi, which are achievable. One of these is the pressure for Pôle emploi to 'dematerialise' their services, as part of a general push from the French government and the EU to modernise service access. This involves automating and digitising time-consuming tasks, such as responding to emails which consume thousands of hours of caseworker time each year. The goal is for intelligence emploi to take over the management of these tasks by dividing emails into the less important (which the system will automatically answer) and the more important, which will be sent to a caseworker with a notice that it should be addressed quickly. This is anticipated to save 15-30 minutes of caseworker time each day, which can be spent on unemployment counselling, CV-building, job search advice, employer networking and so on.

3.6 Australia JSCI

Context and background

The Job Seeker Classification Instrument (JSCI) was the result of development work and research conducted in Australia in 1997, before coming into active use in 1998, making JSCI one of the oldest (if not the oldest) continuously running ALMP. At this time, JSCI was a questionnaire filled out by the jobseeker as part of their applications process to receive social welfare payments. JSCI identified 18 factors of importance which determined if an unemployed person was likely to find work (age, educational attainment, language and literacy, geographic location etc.). JSCI was (and still is) administered through Centrelink, the Australian government's key unemployment agency, responsible for social transfers and implementing ALMP's. Much of the questionnaire has remained intact over time; questions are added rather than taken away.

The development of JSCI was spurred on by a spike in unemployment in the early 90s, hitting a peak of 11.2% in 1993, though this had already fallen to 8% by the time JSCI was being piloted in 1997 and would continue to fall to a historic low of 4% in 2008. The global financial crisis led to another spike, and since then, unemployment in Australia has stubbornly held to a rate between 5-7%. However, apart from the rate of unemployment (a ubiquitous problem in all countries), JSCI was created to categorise, classify, and metricise Australia's unique problem: geography.

With 7.7 million square kilometres of land to administer, Australia is comparable to Brazil (8.5 million square km), or China (9.5 million square km). As a reference point, France, the largest country in Europe, is only 643,000 square km. Australia's population and population density are also significantly lower than all these countries, with Brazil, for example, having 209.5m people and a population density of 25 per square km. Australia, by comparison, has only 24.99m people and a population density of 3.2 per square km. While large tranches of Australia are not inhabited, the parts that are inhabited are spread over its entire landscape, with most of the population living in 6 clusters near or in major cities. If one of these clusters is suffering from economic decline, it is almost impossible for someone to get a job in another cluster without moving from one to another. JSCI was intended to track which clusters were struggling to give jobseekers and caseworkers a realistic picture of the problem they were facing.

In the modern era, Australia is moving with the current trend to modernise and digitise services. JSCI is transitioning to an online-only system, and most services will be delivered digitally by 2022, as part of a programme called digital-first. In many ways, this is a 21st-century answer to the geographical problem first identified in the 20th century. The goal is threefold:

- Make unemployment assistance services sustainable.
- Focus on disadvantaged areas, groups, people, communities
- Improve compliance from jobseekers by establishing a system of mutual obligations

Australia, then, is confronting the same problem facing many other nations: the problem of rationing care. With such a vast area to administer over, limited money for welfare transfers, limited numbers of caseworkers, disadvantaged areas with high unemployment (etc.), Centrelink is seeking a 21st-century algorithmic digital tool that will help them to provide care when and where it is needed.

Inside Job Seeker Classification Instrument (JSCI)

JSCI currently takes the form of a questionnaire that has 49 questions, and while many of the questions have undergone small changes since it was piloted in 1997, the factors under consideration are less elastic. The unemployed person fills this questionnaire out as part of their application for unemployment, and each answer awards a corresponding number of points. The points given for each answer are reviewed every two years in a process called re-estimation, which ensures that points remain relevant to current contexts.

With higher life expectancy, the pension age set to increase to 67, and a work culture that encourages people to work into retirement, questions around age give fewer points compared to when JSCI was first piloted. Questions around transport capabilities, geographical location, and digital literacy have only grown in prominence, and are more heavily weighted. Certain questions, such as the jobseeker's ethnicity, refugee status, disability status, Indigenous status, or the number of criminal convictions are optional for privacy and ethical reasons.

The caseworker assigned to each person examines their score (aggregated number of points) and sorts people into one of three streams, based on their barriers to employment.

- a) Low barriers to employment
- b) Moderate barriers to employment
- c) High barriers to employment, disadvantaged

In addition, answers to certain questions, particularly questions relating to health or disability can trigger an automatic Employment Services Assessment (ESAt). An ESAt is a detailed and comprehensive assessment of a jobseeker's capabilities to find work and is conducted by a health care professional. Depending on the results of the ESAt, the jobseeker may be removed from the ordinary process of sorting into one of the streams and sent to Disability Employment Services instead.

Since 2018, this process has been accompanied by having the data fed into a LOGIT profiling model in addition to a reading of the information by a caseworker. The goal of this algorithm is to identify job seekers who are likely to become long-term unemployed (12 months). Its accuracy in determining this has not been published recently, but a report from 2005 (prior to the algorithm) stated that Australian profiling has a 90.3% accuracy rate in identifying who will be long-term unemployed. In moving to a digital-first platform, the goal is to streamline the accessibility, usability, and utility of its services. By

having the questionnaire filled out digitally, and analysed algorithmically, this enables applicants to be sorted into streams and assigned to a caseworker who can tailor their advice to the specific needs of the jobseeker in question.

JSCI and conditionality

Nevertheless, JSCI has significant issues, around transparency, autonomy, and risk. JSCI is marketed as a risk analysis and profiling tool; however, it is not neutral in this process as it classifies jobseekers as 'problems' which need to be solved. In taking this stance, the Australian profiling system has a tendency to aggressively trample the autonomy of the jobseekers it is supposed to help, by forcing them to apply for jobs that are not a part of their career trajectory, ignoring or reducing the importance of caring responsibilities and not taking the jobseekers perspective into account. Consequently, a job seeker could end up required to apply for jobs with very long commute times, even if they have an ill relative or a child to take care of. JSCI is also an opaque system; its accuracy rate is not publicly published, leaving considerable questions of efficacy and transparency unanswered.

3.7 Towards an archetypical of 1st generation profiling algorithms

The five algorithms explored in this section are broadly representative of the various approaches used across the OECD (Desiere, et al, 2019), representative in that these classification algorithms are based on static or updated survey data, rather than on live, continuously updated registry data, that they deploy a variety of different approaches, with subtle distinctions in their ambitions. When taken together, despite their differences, each algorithm is connected to a profiling tool used by the leviathan state to ration care.

Archetypical LTU sorting/profiling algorithms

The origin of these algorithms lies in the nexus of relations between PES, economists, data scientists and international benchmarking agencies. The attraction to these instruments is that they dehumanise the discrimination, throwing the unpleasant business of sorting citizens into a black box. In the next section, we pry open the black box to explore the ethical implications in, on, and around algorithm design.

4.0 Identifying key concepts and concerns

The purpose of this report to undertake an ethical, social, theological, technical review of first generation PES algorithms and data use. In section two we reviewed some practical case examples, before exploring the generic dominant design (Utterback and Abernathy, 1975). Here we examine the key ethical, social, theological and technical concerns in, on and around 1st generation algorithmic welfare.

There is a significant and growing body of studies on the ethics of algorithmic systems, and yet there is relatively little on algorithmic welfare (Dencik and Kaun, 2020), so this section aspires to articulate the broader literature into our work on PES algorithms and data use. We present this as a terrain of inquiry, rather than imposing unity, a single theoretical framework, or even a single list of principles and values to aid algorithmic welfare design. We start by looking into the 'black box', before exploring the larger social life. Core issues of algorithmic bias, fairness, data privacy, transparency, scrutable, accountability infuse all discussions about automated decision making. Whilst the issues are shared, the two tribes of disciplines working (Snow, 1959) on these issues operate independently of each other. Unsurprisingly, data scientist, functional managers and statisticians focus predominantly on those ethical issues that can most easily be framed and addressed technically: including how to make algorithmic systems more interpretable and reliable, and address or moderate issues of privacy and data protection. These professional and technocratic groups do not see the ethical responsibility for their work residing with them or their professional community. Philosophy and ethics researchers tend to focus on questions about the moral significance of algorithmic systems that could potentially exist in the future, with less attention paid to the practical ethical challenges of current systems. We noticed in our review that academic law literature has grappled more substantially with the practical philosophical and ethical issues presented by current systems – particularly issues of privacy and fairness.

4.1 Ethical issues in PES algorithm design

Understanding the ethical issues around PES algorithms begins with understanding and acknowledging biases encoded into all algorithms. There is a natural fear that the biases of the algorithms authors, later-day mechanical turks, turn into a durable invisible form of discrimination (Steiner, 2012; Kavanagh et al, 2015), or more directly that the algorithm feeds the discrimination of the labour market through into the services offered by the state to shield individuals from the worst excesses of the market (Boland & Griffin, 2015). In the transition from human-made evaluations into machine-made judgements many of our tools for identifying and deliberating over human-made evaluations into machine-made judgements. Whilst it can appear that human autonomy is replaced with machine-made judgements, it is better to think of human decision making arising in the design and decision to implement an algorithm, and then becoming marginalised. To bowdlerise Winston Churchill's reflection on architecture- we shape the algorithms we build, thereafter they shape us – hence the focus on surfacing the ethical issues in PES algorithm design.

Algorithmic decision-making, or even algorithmic supported decision-making can make complex decisions cheaper, faster, and at a greater scale than human decision making. As such systems become more ubiquitous they also become more accountable (Diakopoulos, 2016).

The Relative Roles of Individuals and Technology in Decision-Making

The Role of Algorithms in Decision-Making (Martin, 2019)

Many of these arise in design, which is a distinctly human activity. Hidden inside every algorithm is the wisdom, prejudice and biases of its designer, and the variety of influences in which they are shaped (Kitchin and Dodge, 2011). Famously New York has racist bridges (Caro, 1974), designed at the insistence of Robert Moses to prevent buses, and the poorer, often non-white customers from commuting to the city. Car airbags are designed for men (Bose et al, 2011), the height of kitchen sinks are standardised for women (Criado Perez, 2019), voice recognition software is better at understanding men than women (Tatman, 2017). This is true of older mathematical operations, so for example the use of zero was forbidden by pre-enlightenment theological injunctions (Griffin, forthcoming 2021) and the very development of statistics was nested in the odious pseudo-science of eugenics (Cowan, 1972). Those who develop algorithms are usually not present or even visible to those who use them, as Garfinkel ethnomethodological study of a road junction showed- someone sets the timer on a traffic lights and is never seen again (Lieberman, 2013). As more decisions and a greater proportion of human decisions are made by algorithmic systems- from loan approvals to medical diagnostic decisions, the agency of these design bias becomes ever more significant, durable and formalised. This is particularly true of algorithms attempts to predicts contingent behavioural outcomes, relying on historical criteria which in practice reinforces past biases, in a way that discounts the possibility of significant change. Understanding the ethical issues around PES algorithms begins with understanding and acknowledging biases designed into the all algorithms, and incorporating the ability to reform, refine and improve deployed algorithms based on careful oversight and evaluation work. The inability to reform algorithms can exacerbate negative impacts (O'Neil, 2016), particularly in machine learning algorithms that allow no further human intervention and that learn from existing data and the consequent mistakes in existing data, in a vicious cycle.

Considering the distributed roles within decision-making between people and things such as algorithms, raises important questions about accidents. Whilst in a purest sense, algorithms, like all sciences have no accidental properties (Aristotle, 1994), a technology cannot exist without its accident (Virilio, 2007). The invention of the ship, is the invention of the shipwreck and similarly, PES algorithms contain the possibility of mistakes. Algorithms that categorise individuals are highly susceptible to two types of mistakes. False positives are the first form of mistake, where the wrong label is placed on someone. So, for example, if someone is identified being pregnant when they are not, being a terrorist when they are not; or being labelled as being unlikely to gain work in six months when they are not. Alternatively, false negatives, incorrectly exclude someone from a category. A false negative is a test that misses a real pregnancy, an actual terrorist or someone highly likely to become longterm unemployed. False negatives entail the algorithmic decision examining individuals and failing to labelling them as the correct and fitting category. Both false positive and negatives are present in human and machine categorisation practices, what is important to know is the rate of both, and the implications of misclassification.

The legitimacy of PES algorithms comes from the perception of accuracy, the sense that the tools are successful at capturing those at risk of LTU, a sense that is not borne out by examinations of the complex efficacy of these algorithms (McGuinness, et al., 2014, 2019; Riipinen, 2011). The limited, and muddled reporting of accuracy raises questions about the real-world functioning of these tools.

Country	Accuracy
Ireland- PEX	50-69% (challenge of old data)
Austria	80-85% (ethics interesting....)
Denmark- Job Barometer	66% (not enough data, but exciting maths)
Finland	89%
Belgium	67% (advanced case... exciting...)
Netherlands- WorkProfiler	70%
New Zealand	63-83%

Overview profiling models - OECD.org (Desiere et al., 2019)

Although this table is drawn from the OECD reported accuracy rates (Desiere et al., 2019), it is unclear the method of reporting, if it is standardized and thus comparable operational accuracy. Such data would normally be reported with a method statement, and more significant effort to accessibly explain to non-expert users at the point of reporting what this accuracy measure actually means. Without this, the measure is meaningless and comes over as a political gesture to appear accurate, whilst being opaque and obtuse about actual accuracy. In order to develop a clear picture of how profiling algorithms work in the real world it is necessary to delve into the terminology which surrounds the various measure used to quantify accuracy in the world of data science. Data scientists have a range of precise terms and approaches to address the terrain of accuracy, error, sensitivity, specificity around the real-world function of algorithms.

In the little methodological literature reported on the UK, Austrian and Belgian tools, it appears that what is being reported is a measure called 'forecast accuracy' which is the percentage of your overall target group which your tool captures. The term "forecasting accuracy" (Tashman, 2000) usefully has the modifier 'forecasting' which serves to moderate the perception of certainty conveyed in terming the measure accuracy. A layperson, or even an experienced social policy researcher is likely to think that an 80% accuracy means that two in every ten people that are profiled are misclassified. Forecast accuracy measures the percentage of the LTU unemployed the tool captures, however it does not capture those misclassified.

Two by two contingency table

(Swets, 1988)

High accuracy rates suggest that at risk of LTU profiling is highly **specific** but not **sensitive**.

That means a positive result is almost always true, but a negative result is sometimes false.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{\text{No. of true positives}}{\text{No. of those profiled who really were at risk of LTU}} = \text{"how many at risk of LTU did we find"}$$

$$A+B+C+D = N$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = A/(A+B)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{\text{Number of true positives}}{\text{No. of those profiled who really were not at risk of LTU}} = \text{"how many not at risk of LTU did we clear"}$$

$$\text{Specificity} = A/C$$

Accuracy report this way focuses on the percentage of those at risk of LTU (A+C, true positives + false negatives) that the tool correctly forecasts (the A+B), rather than those that are missed as false positives and false negatives. PES profiling algorithms assign everyone in the sample N with a score for their likelihood of becoming LTU, however the operators then must set a boundary on these scores which delineates the cut-off point between high and low risk. We surmise, that this threshold is cast based on the PES caseworker capacity, and the level of the threshold dictates both the forecast accuracy and corresponding error rate of the algorithm technology. The operational implications of this are made very clear in a recent UK feasibility study (Matty, 2013), detailed in this table:

Table 3 Operational effectiveness of ranking

	Size of targeted segment	
	Top 8%	Top 30%
Number of target segment that reach LTU	29	64
Number of target group that do not reach LTU	58	262
Total number of LTU	91	91
Total number of non-LTU	994	994
Proportion of all LTU captured by segmentation	32%	70%
Proportion of all non-LTU receiving 'unnecessary' support	6%	26%

Note: Model applied to test dataset (n = 1,085).

The impact of moving the threshold in a sample of 1,085 radically altered the proportion of those misclassified as false positive and thus recipients of additional caseworker support that individuals did not need. What is not captured by the measure forecasting accuracy is the extent to which the algorithm fails to identify individuals who do need additional support. In the UK study 30% of all those who went on to become LTU were misclassified as low risk a fact which has profound real-world implications for the management of LTU and the function of PES. Were the algorithm and this particular tool employed to ration access to caseworker services in a population of 250,000 unemployed people it would mean that 75,000 individuals would not receive the extra support the model claims ration effectively. A study of the Austrian profiling system found similar inconsistencies between what was deemed to be the accuracy rate of the model and the error rate generated by the model and suggested that these decisions were tacit and value-laden (Allhutter et al. 2020). Furthermore, this study highlights the real-world impact of these choices on jobseekers. In the Austrian model being in a distinct group means you are granted or denied access to labour market supports which means that being classified as a false positive or negative will have a profound effect in your chances of gaining employment. There is no evidence, or curiosity if a human over-ride of the algorithmic recommendation can address these lack of rigour. A more transparent approach to the effectiveness of these profiling tools would be desirable, particularly reporting accuracy rates against the population. A recent study of the latest Belgian AI profiling tool suggested that different statistical approaches an increases forecast accuracy by 12 %, but again the detail on what constituted accuracy was not clear (Desiere & Struyven, 2020). The cost of miscategorisation must be weighted up against the stated benefits of profiling in making delivery more efficient, that more costly, intensive services are targeted at jobseekers most at risk of becoming LTU, and in providing detailed information on the employment barriers facing jobseekers (OCED, 2018). Misclassifying four individuals to capture one correct prediction is not efficient, when the deadweight costs of providing unnecessary services is incorporated into the calculation. Beyond this, there is little evidence that these algorithms are used to offer detailed personalised interventions, and that given the low accuracy such interventions would be wise.

Limited reporting and concern for reporting on the accuracy and misclassification problems of PES algorithms suggests the technology works primarily to prevent caseworkers load from being overwhelmed, and that once that objective is achieved there may be little incentive to examine the algorithms function much further.

4.2 Ethical issues on PES algorithm design

Algorithms which function in the 'real' world are social by their nature. It is not that they are created and then act on the social world, but that the social world is present at their inception, it is the social world which brings them into being and it is present at every stage of their design and implementation. It is these social algorithms which subsequently begin the process of re-shaping the world to which they are connected often in unforeseeable and unpredictable ways, acting more as engines rather than cameras (McKenzie, 2006). Seen from this perspective it is not a question of whether bias is or is not coded into algorithms but rather a set of several questions about the characteristics of the bias which must be present. How much bias, what motivates it, what world view is it shaped by, and what effect

does it have, are just some of the many questions we could ask of its characteristics? However, this is not to suggest that acknowledging the social, institutional, political, and economic influences exerted on and by algorithms is a panacea for developing real understanding about their form and function or that we should ignore the technical details of algorithm design. Instead of seeing the social and the technical as separate, we suggest that the social, institutional, political and economic influences which surround algorithms are the algorithm, they are the reason for its being and this being the case it follows that bias is coded into the very existence of the technology (Seaver 2013).

The contextual design process unfolds as algorithms are 'edited, revised, deleted and restarted, shared with others, passing through multiple iterations stretched out over time and space' (Kitchin and Dodge 2011). This 'messy' design processes are complemented by a range of other activities such as data selection, data scrubbing, researching concepts, tuning parameters, raising finance (Kitchin, 2018) and general organisational interventions. These processes are surrounded by system of thought and forms of knowledge, embedded in particular political economies, their cultural, legal, institutional, organisational and political subjectivities. This socio-technical description of the design of algorithms goes far beyond the description of an objective technology suggesting that algorithms are relational, contingent, and contextual in nature (Kitchin 2018). In this line of thinking, Leslie (2019) notes several sources for potential bias in the design process including, data training, data sampling, data weighting and modelling. Danks and John (2017) also note the potential for bias during the early stages and highlight the 'hidden' aspects of bias as we only see the end product and not the data used in its production (Danks & John 2017). This concern with transparency is shared by a wide range of contributors suggesting that if we could see what was in the algorithms, we could limit the biased effects they have on real-world outcomes.

The sense that algorithmic decision-making appears rational, clean and mistake-proof, that few people understand how they work and so convey upon them a special, proprietary inscrutable mystique makes them both less open to examination, and questioning. This is particularly true of the output of the algorithm is considered final and not open to appeal.

Of critical significance is thus; who does the designing and who is excluded. As PES profiling algorithms they involve complex techniques of mathematics, statistics, and modelling, algorithms have naturally been designed by data scientists and statisticians but have also had input from economists and policy makers. Conventionally algorithms have had appeal for governments and the public because they are seen to remove human error and bias from decision making. Algorithms however suffer from a kind of Mechanical Turk problem, which refers to a chess playing machine built in the late 18th century, the Turk was able to defeat famous statesmen and chess masters. However, the Turk was a fake, a chess master was hidden inside the machine and was making the moves; we argue that algorithms work in this same way. They appear to make decisions unimpeded by human influence, but there is in fact a human within the algorithm.

Methodologically, there is a (somewhat oversimplified) split between the positivist and interpretivist visions of how research ought to be done. In the positivist vision, only empirical evidence which can be scientifically verified counts towards knowledge building; opposing this is the interpretivist vision which contends that knowledge is an abstraction, and that there are a multitude of ways to see it, not all of which can be utilised scientifically. The people who construct algorithms generally fall into a more positivist way of seeing the world, for example in the Nuffield Foundation Report on the ethics of algorithms the authors say:

"In general there seems to be a 'culture of disengagement' among technical researchers and engineers, who generally do not see ethical and societal questions raised by technology as their responsibility" (Whittlestone et al, 2019, p.46).

If we are to build an ethical algorithm, we must carefully consider our own values as they will have a great influence on the design and inner workings of the algorithm while resisting this culture of disengagement. We are committed to the fundamental values underpinning the foundation of the European Union: respect for human dignity and human rights, freedom, democracy, equality and the rule of law (EU Charter; Latour). We begin from the perspective that if the algorithm is to be ethical,

that it must be inclusive, and incorporate the voices and perspectives of those who will use it. Of primary importance are the caseworkers, counsellors, unemployment advisors (etc.) and the unemployed themselves.

In the former case we know that the implementation of algorithmic systems within PES' can fail (as in Finland and Austria) because the unemployment advisors refuse to utilise them, or public opposition was mobilised. This can be for many reasons, but in the Finnish case the algorithm was perceived to be crude, inhumane, and ineffective (Riipinen 2011). In the Austrian case, data protection and the very idea of profiling held more sway (Allhutter, et al, 2020). Caseworkers have deep institutional knowledge, and an intuitive understanding of how to navigate the problematics of unemployment, the algorithm sidestepped this and simply categorised the unemployed as low, medium, or high risk of long-term unemployment. PES workers place a high value on their capacity to exercise discretion in the provision of welfare, and if an algorithm is to be successful it must work with PES caseworkers, not attempt to sidestep their expertise.

In algorithm design, the unemployed have conventionally been seen as an inactive, but malleable source of potential for the market, who are suffering with issues of welfare dependency. We must invert this perspective and see the unemployed through the lens of our European values: as people with rights, values, families, caring responsibilities, emotions, skills, and talents, but most of all we must see them as juridical individuals capable of making good decisions that are in their own best interest. Our goal is to provide them with a tool, such that the labour market can be better apprehended, which in turn will enable better informed choices to be made.

As noted earlier, motivating the development of PES profiling algorithms was the perceived necessity of rationing access to overwhelmed caseworkers against the backdrop of the GFC. Once the algorithms appeared to segment the unemployed into levels of job readiness, caseworker access could be managed. Driving adoption is considerable institutional support for profiling from the OECD and Worldbank.

It takes time for such algorithms to be developed, tested and scaled for operation in day-to-day frontline services, sometimes years, often when the pressure to ration has diminished. These tools work on the basis that future risk can be assessed from past behaviour. The models use data on a range of sources and develop what are supposed to be key indicators of likely-hood of exit from unemployment. Once in place, even in the face of evidence that the algorithm does not function as describe, institutional inertia sustains the deployment. Ireland is a particularly good example of this- deployed in 2012, based on survey data from 2006 a review in 2014 concluded that the PES algorithm were unlikely to predict a person's probability of long-term unemployment, yet the technology is still in place in 2020. In the face of a rapidly contracting Irish labour market, declining from 16% unemployment to 5% in six years, LTU dropped precipitously, something the algorithm could not envisage. Beyond this, the individual measures such as previous history of LT unemployment, previous participation in job creation programmes, age, number of children, low level of educational attainment, literacy and numeracy difficulties and geographical location do not stand apart from one another as individual constructs, most are strongly correlated to each other. Therefore, if we have sufficient data about past behaviour, we will be able to predict future outcomes. Given the widespread adoption of algorithm technology across a range of European economies the promise of the ability to predict future behaviour is a powerful idea, no matter how flawed or biased the basic assumptions which underpin it.

While focus on bias is normally based on what variables used, a broader consideration would explore what data is not there. Rarely is the labour market demand, employment data brought into calculations, constructing the problem of unemployment as a personal problem interior to the unemployed, unrelated to context, to history, path dependencies, culture, and family. This illusion fails to grasp that the very construct of unemployment is the opposite, constructing it as an impersonal market failure (Jahoda, 1932). In the past twenty years, Europe has been struck by two economic crises- GFC and Covid-19- both arbitrary and capricious cleavers swiping blindly at the labour market. Statistical modelling needs to account for changes in the economy and therefore requires regular updating to preserve its predictive power (O'Connell et al., 2009).

The lens cast onto the labour market is usually at a bounded territory that is far larger than the geographic reach of an individual, their family and home- so the unit of analysis, problematisation, metricisation is usually national or NUTS2/3 regional, yoking large groups of individuals together for average treatment.

4.4 Ethical issues around PES algorithm design

One of the most ethically contentious aspects of PES algorithms is their goal driven nature. In most cases PES algorithms develop a profile of the unemployed using techniques of risk assessment, pattern detection, and probability to evaluate the likelihood that given traits, characteristics, or attributes will lead to long-term unemployment (Boskoski, P. & Boshkoska, 2020). Algorithms have often fallen victim to Goodhart's Law that "when a measure becomes a target, it ceases to be a good measure". Algorithms are often driven by the need to solve political problems, such as unemployment, healthcare provision, grading (etc.), but in trying to solve these problems they produce irrational outcomes. Such as the tendency for unemployment algorithms to drive people into poorly paid, insecure, temporary work, thus weakening people's future position in the labour market. For an algorithm to be ethical, it only needs to allow us to see the market and should not be goal or solution oriented.

The reasons for this are myriad. Markets are chaotic systems, and do not by necessity follow procedural rules. The labour market is a colossus of people, data, information, and decision-making on a global scale. Every part of this system influences every other part of it in a manner not unlike the Butterfly Effect, and connections are being established, destroyed, and changed all the time. Algorithms by contrast are a complex system, taking large amounts of data and processing it according to given procedural rules. While the amount of data may be vast, it is finite and because of this can only ever produce a snapshot of the chaotic system that is the labour market.

ALMPs were a concerted effort by various governments to reduce unemployment in the aftermath of the global financial crisis of 2007/8, and much of the discourse referred to issues of welfare dependency. The goal of ALMPs then was to 'activate' the 'inactive' elements of the workforce who may have grown complacent and given up attempting to find work. Evaluation of ALMPs has been mixed, trending toward negative, and it is questionable if issues of dependency were widespread, as a body of qualitative evidence (Boland and Griffin, 2015) argues that most of those who are unemployed become, and stay unemployed due to circumstances beyond their control. Through characterising the unemployed as dependent upon welfare, ALMPs were able to gain the political legitimacy necessary to participate in and influence the labour market; which they used to reduce or limit the autonomy of the unemployed by requiring them to apply for any, and all work which was available, with poor long-term results.

We contend that there is dependency of a different kind being established, the dependency of governmental decision making upon algorithmic logics. As outlined in the previous section's discussion on values, studying social problems algorithmically changes how we think about them, and there is a subtle shift happening in the delivery of governance. As algorithms become more salient and sophisticated, there is a danger that social, political, cultural, and even symbolic issues will be seen as computational problems. With the advent of COVID-19 there has been a shift in the balance of power toward the digital and algorithmic, and States are increasingly investing in digital, rather than physical infrastructure, which produces future dependency on algorithmic problem solving. One example is facial recognition technology, often used for its capacity to covertly surveil criminals and deter crime; but this is a solution-oriented technology that sidesteps deeper sociological and ethical questions. Spending money on facial recognition technology to catch criminals, as opposed to addressing access to housing, education, healthcare (etc.), which are the root causes of crime seems illogical.

Progressing past this does not involve further subsumption into algorithmic logics, there does not exist an algorithm that would be technically, scientifically, mathematically, or statistically advanced enough to "solve" unemployment, crime, education, or other social issues. As we have argued, it is this solution-oriented mindset that produces the problems to begin with, and for the same reason: they develop an incomplete picture of the market, and then require that people perform to that incomplete

picture. ALMPs and their accompanying algorithms ought not to be participants in the labour market, it is sufficient that they provide information and make the labour market more transparent. The result of our critique then is that our algorithm is best thought of as a tool or instrument, there are many ways to use a tool, and there are many tools, different people will use the same tool in different ways, it facilitates, enables, and illuminates; and perhaps most importantly use of it is wholly optional.

These differences become pronounced when PES algorithms are used without human oversight, where human agency and autonomy is diminished or removed entirely and when the objectives for algorithmic decision-making emphasises the entire network over any individual within the system.

5.0 Recommendations on design

These multiple ethical, social, theological and technical concerns and challenges in the design and use PES algorithms must be given thoughtful consideration so as to realise the potential benefits of this emerging technology to society. Through surfacing and addressing ethical concerns, designers and users can promote positive long-term adoption, and can avoid the significant negative consequences associated with algorithmic decision making- potential damage to the unemployed, the users, PES and indeed to the reputation of data science. There are particular and concrete measures that can be taken to address these ethical problems and mitigate their associated risks. This report is primarily concerned with support the technical team in understanding the ethical, social and theological issues in and around the development and use of first generation PES algorithms. In this, we probed the commonly used algorithms provided in Deliverable 3.1. and make the following observations:

For whom the algorithm tolls

These first generation algorithms focus on addressing PES process needs, particularly preventing PES caseworker service from being overwhelmed. This is a classic agency problem, where the PES are automatically assumed to act in best interests of unemployed people, but can if a conflict of interest arises, such as happens when PES is overwhelmed, act in the interest of the PES. As such the algorithms do not directly work on the core PES challenge of supporting LTU, rather they work on an unrelated symptom of high rates of general unemployment which cyclically arise in certain countries. The needs of the unemployed, or LTU are not addressed by the algorithms. Our analysis is conducted from the primary ethical understanding of HECAT, that we are developing a system that **works with and not on** unemployed people. In doing this we hope to provide **tools and not solutions** to PES that will enable them to assist unemployed people in making decisions on returning to work or education via a visualised labour market, that align with European values. At a minimum, unemployed people should be consulted and engaged to support the development of tools that impact them; those who carry their voice and advocate for them, without other attendant responsibilities are a potential second best option. In a similar vein, caseworkers should be engaged to co-produce the tool. The tool must do more than ration caseworkers, to prevent them from being overwhelmed, rather it needs to make a positive contribution to caseworker and unemployed person interaction, adding value and insight.

The tool must identify a core (rather than a subsidiary, adjacent or symptomatic) problem to be addressed

The tool must have a client that is both PES and the unemployed person, with user determined scale (eg. local/regional/national) choice

From thin to thick

First generation PES algorithms rely on “thin data”, a handful of variables stripped of any richer contextual meaning, often developed from static, ad-hoc survey work. These algorithms rarely use existing data infrastructures. In this, they cannot really be considered big data approaches, as they do not exploit the full potential of big data based on live, continually updated, massive and complex data sets. As addressed in D3.1 (Boskoski & Boshkoska, 2020) key to the quality of any algorithm and the mathematics behind it is considered to be the quality of the datasets that are used and available, dynamic processes and assessment of the model and selecting the most suitable candidates for developing the model. The purpose of profiling in most cases is to determine how far a person is from the labour market, that is, how long it should take them to enter or re-enter the workplace. While profiling can assist state agencies in rationing scarce resources for example by providing more support to those who are deemed further away from the labour market and having minimum intervention for those who are likely to find employment in a short space of time. Such a scenario is one of the reasons given to justify profiling, however the mathematics and predictive nature of any algorithm used for PES

can additionally assist in predicting the future costs of providing social welfare supports for unemployed people, or support private sector contractors in pricing tenders to supply PES so there is an economic rationalisation that can also be attributed to these models. Additional limitations on statistical analysis is its difficulty in predicting human nature outside of 'rational choices'. As statistics is a methods of visualising ranges of data in a succinct manner and making inferences through mathematical calculations, it is impossible, and undesirable, to collect every piece of information from every individual in order to perform a statistical study. Therefore, predictions are made on sample sizes and questions are asked or data is collected based on the needs of the compiler. There are then biases imposed on all data and how it is used.

The tool should exploit a big-data approach, so focus on using (and improving upon) existing data infrastructures

Humble data should be presented, where weaknesses and limitations are presented with the data

Statistics as a means of understanding a population

While statistics is a valuable discipline for counting, measuring, predicting, regularising variabilities and visualising large datasets succinctly, it is limited by its accuracy in measuring complex human traits (such as happiness or quality of employment).

Statistics and statistical modelling work well with unambiguous data where little or no 'best guess' judgement is required. There is a greater need for judgement when human traits are involved, which is the root of biases that are often encoded into the collection and measurement of data. While this limitation of statistics may appear obvious to some the fact that statistics "statistics is still just information, and only the starting point to real understanding of the world" (Spiegelhalter, 2019, p.10) is an often overlooked circumstance. Using purely statistical analysis and models makes inferences from data about how a future situation might appear based on past data, but does little to explain the deeper conditions of the situation as it happens in a real-world scenario. In this line of reasoning, if PES are using statistical modelling to determine the situation of unemployed people it could be argued that it will adequately serve a function of determining the resources required (finance, personnel etc...) to service levels of unemployment but may not accurately determine variables, indicators and metrics concerning the gaining of suitable employment by an individual. These variables are a mixture between low ambiguous facts (no of jobs available, state of the labour market, economic growth, regional economies etc...) and personal perspectives (what is a suitable job, what is a good quality job). The limitation of any statistical modelling involving employment/unemployment will be the non-rational or individualised nature of human perceptions on employment.

The abstraction of statistics is a map, not a the terrain, and so statistical representation of society should be humble and circumspect. Current privileging of overly simplified, totemistic numbers (such as the unemployment rate or GDP) turn these numbers from cameras that observe into engines that drive performance and action. Add to this the politician's syllogism- 'We must do something. this is something. therefore, we must do this' (Chen, 2007), statistics take on a performative stance. Performative (Austin, 1967; Butler, 1990) in the sense that statistics actually make the thing they purport to observe.

Singular approaches should be avoided, as they give an unjustified sense of totalising comprehensiveness that leads to performativity problems.

Auditability and transparency

There is considerable potential for PES algorithms to cause harm, and designers must understand, as best they can the multiple risks. Prevention is an important element of addressing such risks, but inevitably, in practice, new risks will emerge and so a strategy that incorporates early recognition and mitigation is as important. Central to auditability is supporting literacy in algorithmic decision making- offering accessible and fulsome explanations of how the system works. Such a strategy must also recognise the individual, the population, the PES, and the political as important stakeholders; all requiring sensitive and transparent engagement and response measures. All need passive and active recourse, with a direct feedback loop into the broader system. An important component of such an approach is to create processes and responsibilities around the auditability of the algorithm and its use. In universities and hospitals it is common to evaluate the human impact of research, and as such impacts are increasingly being mediated by algorithms, we increasingly need better approaches to understand the ethical shortcomings of automated systems. Such review measures, should be aligned to the principles of natural justice- being open and transparent within general operating constraints.

Auditability processes of autonomous technical systems differs from human analogue systems in important ways. Technical systems can directly incorporate auditability processes into the system, capturing inputs, and undertaking self-evaluation and scrutiny as it goes. Such approaches can be automated within the system, but also in the human-system interface, and with human centred recourse available when anomalies are detected, and escalated. A review process thus has significant baseline data to undertake its work in scoping out how best to update and improve the system in use.

Additionally, organisations can seek to collect user feedback in and around ethical sensitivities that are relevant to their system. Again, regular and systematic feedback should be incorporated into an standing internal audit process, as well as being maintained as a separate measure of success or failure. PES algorithms interact with the users in a direct way, and all humans that observe or actively participate should have recourse to provide critical perspectives on the system's design and implementation.

Algorithms with potent agency in people's lives require complete and perfect datasets and; advisory, supportive algorithms that announce their limitations can useful aid rather than make decisions.

Effort should be made to translate the abstract and complex into intuitive and useful; this is true for the data and the methods explanation, along with a commitment to open source- all to support auditability. Evaluation needs to be supported internally to the project and externally.

Recourse

At a minimum, users of PES algorithms both the unemployed and workers in the PES system should be given clear paths for recourse when anomalies arise. People are the most skilled at detecting and understanding problems, anomalies, oversights and biases in the system. For continued political, moral and legal support, algorithmic systems need to do much more to support recourse, offering simple and intuitive ways to gain feedback. Like all technologies, algorithms have and will continue to have their accidents. Sustaining public support requires considerable transparency around failures, and an absence of hubris to ensure advanced users trust and accept the bona fides of those behind the systems. Advancing user trust, through active and empathetic modes of recourse is an essential element in delivering such systems into use.

The institutional programme in support of the development of the HECAT tool should be addressed, with an advisory board, a right to appeal and meaningful oversight.

5.1 In sum

To create a system that is ethical and fair requires input from all stakeholders, but such a scenario can be difficult when dealing with large numbers of individuals.

In Summary, the three outputs that are required for the HECAT system are:

1. Ethical treatment of unemployed people
2. Provide PES workers and unemployed people with useful tools and not solutions
3. Visualise the labour market [supply & demand]

If this is consolidated into the four categories in which citizens are placed then the flow of movement and the reasons for movement are required

1. Employed
2. Self-Employed
3. Unemployed
4. Inactive

The main issue with finding a high quality solution that has a +75% efficacy rate is the quality of data. Data available will most likely determine the system that a designer will choose. Ideally with 'Big Data' and increased processing power it would be advantageous to have unlimited levels and types of data to create the best 'individual labour market' for each person. Under current conditions this appears to be impossible as we have to rely on administrative data that is available in the public domain and through the public/civil service agencies. Issues around this data is the ability to source it and knowing whether or not it exists and in what form. Administrative data in and between government agencies is often disparate and may even be gathered, stored and collated in different formats.

With the limitations of data we need to be innovative in developing the HECAT system. It would be pointless to fall back on traditional statistical models just because they fit the data and we would fail in our commitment to deploy an improved and ethical decision support system. In saying that micro-level data is preferable it is additionally preferable that the system is kept simple and not overly complex. Measuring flows between the 4 categories and flows across the labour market is preferable to focusing the system on the distance a person is from the labour market. Measuring these flows will allow for stakeholders to manipulate variables and follow the potential outcomes, thereby making an informed decision which could be considered to have a high level of self-direction and autonomy and thereby ethical. It would also allow the PES officers to have access to tools rather than solutions, thereby returning them to their original roles as administrators and not recruitment advisors.

6.0 References

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